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A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education

Grant Agreement No. 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000090043

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Short Description	This document presents the transdisciplinary knowledge contributions, prepared by project partners. In addition, the report summarises the key findings of partner countries desk research reports as well as the key findings of the other countries desk research report. In the end, the report provides implications for the ASAP project, based on the findings of conducted desk research.

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Executive Summary

This report presents the results of the desk research conducted within Work Package 2 (WP2) of the Erasmus+ project *ASAP - A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education*, which investigates the relationship between preadolescents (ages 11–13) and social media use, particularly within the educational and school context. The research combined transdisciplinary and transnational approaches and was organised into three main components:

1. transdisciplinary knowledge research establishing the state of the art,
2. country-specific desk research in five partner countries (Italy, Portugal, Czech Republic, Croatia, and Slovenia), and
3. supplementary desk research in selected non-partner countries (Australia, Belgium, Finland, Rhode Island – USA, Spain, United Kingdom).

The overarching aim of the desk research was to create a robust knowledge base that could inform the design of the ASAP Educational Programme, the ASAP Educator Training Programme, and the ASAP Key Recommendations for stakeholders and policymakers.

Transdisciplinary Knowledge Research

With transdisciplinary knowledge research, we aimed to analyse and synthesise the key findings and insights from previous studies and theoretical work related to the identified topics of interest: the cognitive and psycho-social development of preadolescents; the media and digital literacy of (pre)adolescents; social media analysis, including marketing perspectives and social media addiction; the public, private, and common realms; as well as cyberbullying and its prevention.

The transdisciplinary knowledge review demonstrated that preadolescents constitute a uniquely vulnerable population in the digital era, due to the convergence of developmental characteristics, psychosocial needs, and early engagement with social media platforms.

Preadolescence is marked by rapid advances in abstract thinking, executive functioning, and identity formation, yet these capabilities remain immature, leaving children with limited impulse control and heightened susceptibility to peer influence, social comparison, and exclusion. Digital platforms amplify these vulnerabilities by embedding social interactions in feedback-driven systems (such as likes, shares, comments), which can contribute to compulsive use and emotional dependence.

Although social media provides opportunities for creativity, self-expression, and connection, its risks are substantial. These include cyberbullying, exposure to harmful or inappropriate content, privacy violations, algorithmic manipulation, and the reinforcement of unrealistic standards of success or appearance. The review highlighted how preadolescents often fail to distinguish between public and private digital spaces, exposing themselves to reputational risks and unwanted contact.

Media literacy remains underdeveloped, with education on digital risks and responsible online behaviour provided inconsistently across contexts and often dependent on individual teachers or families. At the same time, family-school ecosystems frequently lack coordinated strategies to manage risks, leaving educators without sufficient resources or training. Importantly, research shows that

cyberbullying and online harassment are increasingly experienced at younger ages, with gendered patterns of harm particularly affecting girls.

Overall, the transdisciplinary evidence underscores the urgent need for structured, age-appropriate, and systemic interventions to foster digital resilience, emotional well-being, and critical literacy skills among preadolescents.

Insights from Partner Country Reports

The desk research in the five partner countries identified clear commonalities across contexts, while also highlighting specific challenges shaped by national education systems and social realities.

Preadolescents in all five countries access smartphones and the Internet from an early age, often before age ten, and a significant proportion of preadolescents are active on social media platforms despite formal age restrictions. Daily screen time is substantial, ranging from 1.5 to 3 hours, with clear patterns of problematic use observed in 8–10% of users. This group exhibits signs of excessive engagement, including sleep disturbances, social withdrawal, and reduced life satisfaction.

Cyberbullying and online harassment are widely reported, with between one-quarter and one-half of preadolescents encountering harmful behaviours such as exclusion, threats, hate speech, or the sharing of inappropriate content. Gender differences are evident: girls report more frequent relational aggression, while boys experience more technical threats.

Despite preadolescents' apparent confidence online, digital literacy levels remain low. Preadolescents are often unable to critically assess content, recognise manipulative strategies, or protect their privacy effectively. Parental oversight tends to be limited, particularly in vulnerable contexts, leaving preadolescents at greater risk of exposure to harmful experiences without adequate support.

Education systems in the partner countries are increasingly active in this area, introducing school-based initiatives, teacher training, and prevention programmes. Nevertheless, these efforts are often fragmented, vary between schools, and rely heavily on external actors such as NGOs or EU-funded projects. National legislation on digital safety remains underdeveloped and lacks clear accountability mechanisms for platforms.

Insights from Non-Partner Country Reports

The non-partner country research highlighted more advanced institutional responses in certain contexts, providing valuable comparative insights. Countries such as Australia, the United Kingdom, and Finland have established dedicated agencies, comprehensive national strategies, and legal frameworks to safeguard children online (e.g. Australia's eSafety Commissioner, the UK's Online Safety Bill). These examples demonstrate more structured and coordinated approaches than those generally observed in the partner countries.

A strong emphasis on mental health and well-being was noted in countries such as Australia, Spain, and the United Kingdom, where the relationship between excessive social media use and outcomes such as anxiety, loneliness, and depression is well documented. Gender-specific risks were particularly emphasised in Belgium, Spain and Finland, where evidence shows that preadolescent girls are disproportionately exposed to harmful content (e.g. self-harm, body image pressures, hate speech).

The reports also highlighted structural challenges in implementing media literacy policies. In contexts such as Spain and parts of the United States (e.g. Rhode Island), decentralised education systems mean that effective implementation depends heavily on local initiatives and educators, leading to uneven provision. By contrast, the Belgian case illustrates a decentralised governance model in which media education is primarily developed at linguistic Community level, resulting in differentiated but complementary approaches rather than a uniform national framework. Finally, evidence from the United Kingdom and Australia demonstrated that many preadolescents access platforms earlier than formally permitted by misrepresenting their age, thus entering digital environments without appropriate safeguards.

Implications for the ASAP Project and its Results

The findings have direct implications for the design and delivery of the ASAP project deliverables, such as the ASAP Educational Programme, the ASAP Educator Training Programme and the ASAP Key Recommendations for Stakeholders and Policymakers.

The ASAP Educational Programme should introduce digital education from an early age, using age-appropriate, interactive, and engaging methods that reflect preadolescents' developmental stage. It must go beyond technical skills to include critical digital literacy, emotional resilience, and ethical awareness, with explicit attention to mental health, privacy, gender-sensitive risks, and cyberbullying prevention.

The ASAP Educator Training Programme should prepare teachers and school staff to recognise signs of digital distress, integrate mental health considerations into digital literacy education, and employ practical, adaptable resources that can be used across diverse contexts. Training should also strengthen communication between teachers, students, and parents, while supporting whole-school approaches to prevention and intervention.

Finally, the ASAP Key Recommendations for Stakeholders and Policymakers should address the following aspects: the introduction of formal, age-appropriate digital citizenship education in national curricula; alignment of policy and resources to ensure effective implementation in schools; the creation or strengthening of national coordination mechanisms for child online safety; mandatory, continuous professional development for teachers/educators; cross-sectoral collaboration to address digital well-being holistically; and stronger regulation of platforms to ensure safety-by-design and youth protection.

Conclusion

The desk research highlights the urgency of addressing the intersection between preadolescence, social media use, and digital safety. While opportunities for creativity, connection, and learning exist, the risks associated with early and unsupervised engagement are profound and demand systemic educational and policy responses. The evidence base assembled through this report provides a strong foundation for the ASAP project to develop interventions that are age-appropriate, inclusive, and scalable, while simultaneously advancing broader European and international debates on digital well-being and child protection.

Introduction

The desk research described in this report is part of Work Package 2 (WP2) of the Erasmus+ project *ASAP - A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education*, which combines both desk and field research activities. In WP2, we explored the relationship between preadolescents (children aged 11–13) and social media, focusing particularly on the educational and school context. This investigation was conducted from both a transdisciplinary and a transnational perspective examining the current situation in five partner countries (Italy, Portugal, Czech Republic, Croatia, and Slovenia) to highlight common, cross-cutting features as well as specific local challenges.

The desk research consisted of three main tasks: transdisciplinary knowledge research, desk research in the five partner countries, desk research in selected non-partner countries.

The **transdisciplinary knowledge research** established the current "state of the art" regarding preadolescents, their use of social media and digital devices, and the risks and threats they face online. This serves as a robust theoretical framework and knowledge base for understanding what is already known about the phenomenon under study.

The **desk research in the five partner countries** aimed to provide a detailed snapshot of the phenomenon in each country, recognizing that challenges related to social media and digital device use may vary significantly across different contexts. This research focused on: statistical data, analysis of national research on preadolescents and social media use, good practice examples, and legislation and regulation addressing harmful and violent online behaviour.

The **desk research in non-partner countries** aimed to gather additional insights to complement the findings from the partner countries and to place them within a broader international context.

Following the research conducted, the ASAP Final Desk Research Report is structured in three parts:

1. Transdisciplinary knowledge research,
2. Summary of key findings from the partner countries desk research reports,¹
3. Summary of key findings from the non-partner countries desk research report (Desk Research Other Countries Report).²

Finally, the report outlines the implications of the desk research for the core deliverables of the ASAP project: the ASAP Educational Programme, the ASAP Educator Training Programme and the ASAP Key Recommendations for Stakeholders and Policymakers.

¹ Partner countries desk research reports (for Czech Republic, Croatia, Italy, Portugal and Slovenia) are available on the ASAP website: <https://www.socialmediakids.eu/>

² The Desk Research Other Countries Report is available on the ASAP project website: <https://www.socialmediakids.eu/>

1. Transdisciplinary Knowledge Research

This research aims to analyse and synthesise key findings and insights from previous studies and theoretical work related to the identified topics of interest: the cognitive and psycho-social development of preadolescents; the media and digital literacy of (pre)adolescents; social media analysis, including marketing perspectives and social media addiction; the public, private, and common realms; as well as cyberbullying and its prevention.

This body of research provides a solid theoretical framework and knowledge base for understanding what is already known about the phenomenon under study.

1.1. Cognitive and psycho-social development of preadolescents

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Cognitive development of preadolescents

Human development refers to a series of systematic changes that occur between conception to death. The term systematicity refers to an orderly, patterned and relatively permanent process that excludes momentary and less consistent fluctuations in behaviour, mood, emotions, and thinking. Developmental psychology is a discipline of psychological science that deals with the research of psychological functions and their changes, where it can also focus on the research of the development of individual psychological functions (e. g. the development of cognition). Cognition is a group of mental processes, which in its nature is hierarchically organized, from basic sensory and perceptual processes to elements of executive functioning and cognitive control (Harvey, 2019).

Piaget vs. Vygotsky

When studying cognitive development, it is worth highlighting two great names who shaped the field of developmental psychology in the past century. First is the Swiss psychologist Jean Piaget, who during his long career established one of the most recognized theories of the cognitive development of children and thus also of preadolescents (Hasan et al., 2019; Stoltz, 2018). In order to understand cognitive development, he developed the technique of structured observation (Saracho, 2021), which is still widely used today in the field of developmental psychology and beyond.

After years of research, he published his ideas and defined development through four continuous phases (Winstanley, 2022). In the sensorimotor phase (0 to 2 years), the child gains experience with movement and perception. Towards the end of the phase, he develops the ability to anticipate. This is followed by the pre-operational phase (2 to 7 years) in which the child begins to understand concepts and symbolic representations, which is reflected in the appearance of symbolic play.

In the stage of concrete operations (ages 7 to 11), the child is already capable of taking multiple perspectives. In that time the child is also becoming capable of reciprocity and empathy (Hasan et al., 2019).

This is followed by the stage of formal operations, which begins to develop after the age of eleven or with the beginning of preadolescence. A child who enters the phase of formal operations should be able to arrange objects in a logical sequence, establish empathic friendships, understand that half a litre of water in different glasses has the same amount etc. In the period of preadolescence, the child develops the ability to think abstractly, through the development of deductive and inductive thinking (reasoning from general to specific and vice versa), which affects the ability to solve hypothetical problems through setting and testing hypotheses (Sanghvi, 2020). The characteristic of this stage is also the development of thinking in the direction of dynamism and higher flexibility, which results in the development of critical thinking. The shift from the concrete to the abstract also means developing the ability to think with concepts. The ability to think conceptually means that thinking develops from memorization to understanding. Gardner (1993, cited in Ahmad et al., 2016) says that in this way, development establishes the possibility to transfer knowledge, skills and concepts to new situations.

Researchers point out that the development of thinking does not occur in all individuals in the same way and at the same speed. Some individuals are said to never reach the fourth stage of development (that is, the development of formal operations). Likewise, an individual's ability to think formally and logically can be very limited to a narrow area and impairs the ability to transfer to other areas (Levesque, 2011). In other words, some preadolescents may have already progressed in the stage of formal operations, while others remain in the previous stage, which needs to be taken into account when designing interventions with preadolescents.

As an alternative to Piaget's universal stages of cognitive development, Leo Vygotsky, another great name in developmental psychology, proposed the sociocultural theory of development, which also became one of the key theories in this field (Huang, 2021). He assumed that the development of a child's cognition is significantly influenced by social and cultural factors. Vygotsky assumed that a child learns and develops through social interactions with significant others and that these alone are the key factor for normative cognitive development. Based on these assumptions, he emphasized the importance of language development as a tool for the child's interaction with the environment. He believed that the individuality of thinking develops through communication (dialogues) with others. He also emphasized the importance of children's private speech as a way of self-regulation. At the same time, he attributed great importance to the cultural influences of the environment, where today we would also place television, the Internet, and thus also social networks (Huang, 2021). Vygotsky indicates three new key cognitive formations for the period of adolescence: the development of theoretical thinking, the concept of self-awareness and the ability to develop empathy. The period of adolescence is also marked by the testing of different social roles and the gradual acceptance of adult social roles (Rubtsova, 2020).

Executive function and metacognition in preadolescence

Neurological science strongly emphasizes the existence of so-called (neurologically) sensitive periods in which the brain is particularly sensitive to specific experiences from the environment. Even though the brain in early adolescence is not highly sensitive to the development of early structures, such as impulse control or basic sensorimotor processing, this is a period of development of higher-order cognitive functions, such as executive functions and more complex metacognitive functions (Laube et al., 2020).

Researchers point to the importance of executive functions (especially cognitive flexibility and selective attention) in the protective role against potential consequences of cyberbullying. Cognitive flexibility means the ability to respond quickly and appropriately and to switch between different tasks (Braem & Egner, 2018). Regarding executive functions, Diamond (2013) believes that there are three core executive functions: inhibitory control, working memory, and cognitive flexibility. According to the author, the other functions such as reasoning, planning and organization are built from these three core executive functions.

Morea and Calvete (2022) note that particularly well-developed cognitive flexibility and selective attention skills could prevent a victimization response (either aggressive or depressive). The capacity for selective attention allows the individual to ignore threatening stimuli, while the developed cognitive flexibility allows a greater range in responses to rampant violence. A more flexible individual is more likely to respond to violence functionally (e. g. by seeking help) and not by retreating into depressive symptoms or aggression (which is a common response in less flexible individuals).

Other studies also establish the protective influence of executive functions on preventing the consequences of online harassment, especially the function of cognitive flexibility (Morea & Calvete, 2022).

On the other hand, there is also a connection between a deficit in cognitive flexibility and a higher probability of victimization (Jenkins et al., 2018). Moreover, deficits in cognitive flexibility were related to bullying victimization and perpetration in preadolescents and greater self-reported attention problems longitudinally led to more bullying perpetration and victimization in children and adolescents (Ji et al., 2018). Verlinden et al. (2014) found that children who are not involved in bullying situations as bullies or victims have better scores on intelligence tests. Bullies, victims, and bully-victims have greater difficulty with inhibitory control according to the reports of their parents in the BRIEF Scale. This result suggests a probable deficit in executive functioning related to involvement in bullying situations.

In the period of preadolescence, in addition to the development of executive functions, the ability of metacognition also develops rapidly. Metacognition is a person's ability to reflect, direct and control their own mental representations (dos Santos Kawata et al., 2021; Moses-Payne et al., 2021), which researchers (especially in the field of education) have been intensively researching since the 70s of the last century. In the field of cognitive neuroscience, metacognition is divided into two key components: the first component is metacognitive knowledge, which represents behaviour and knowledge of one's own cognitive processes and awareness of the possibilities of directing and controlling one's own cognition. Another important component represents capabilities, especially the ability to self-control (i. e. the presence of self-regulatory mechanisms), such as planning and adapting to the demands of the environment (Fleur et al., 2021).

At first, it seemed that these abilities begin to develop in humans only in late childhood, but more recent studies establish that metacognitive abilities begin to develop significantly earlier and are innate in a very basic form both in humans and in some other animal species (Goupil & Kouider, 2019).

Metacognitive skills mature from childhood to preadolescence and adolescence with some researchers finding no differences in metacognitive abilities between late adolescents and adults (dos Santos Kawata et al., 2021). During the period of preadolescence, the developing abilities allow the child to become more efficient and less dependent on others in making his own decisions and relying

on his own judgment. Some studies find that compared to children and adolescents, preadolescents are more confident in making their own decisions and male preadolescents rely more often on their own judgment than female preadolescents (Moses-Payne et al., 2021). Another interesting finding demonstrate that 13-year-olds have the highest values of metacognitive abilities (in the age group from 11 to 17 years old) and suggest that by the age of thirteen, metacognition is already strongly developed (dos Santos Kawata et al., 2021). Other studies indicate that adolescents usually outperform preadolescents when measuring metacognitive abilities, which means that abilities, memory abilities in particular, develop during the entire period of adolescence (Selmeczy & Ghetti, 2019).

The consequences of the use and potential abuse of social networks on the cognitive development of preadolescents

The use of social networks, especially when it is intensive, can change cognitive development processes in preadolescents. In general, research finds both negative and positive effects of the use of social networks on the developing cognition of a child or adolescent. Studies relatively consistently establish that the use of screens, social networks, and the Internet can have a significant impact on the ability to maintain attention (the way of processing online information encourages divided attention and increases discovery), memory processes (the way in which information is presented changes the ways of the neurological pathways of acquisition, storage and even evaluation of knowledge), social cognition (the way of interpersonal interactions in connection with changes in the field of self-image and self-esteem) and reward processes in the brain. The available evidence points to the alarming fact that the Internet can cause both acute and permanent changes in various cognitive domains (Firth et al., 2019; Wade et al., 2021; Wilmer et al., 2017).

Scientists demonstrate that executive functions can be trained and developed (Diamond and Ling, 2020; Sala and Gobet, 2020). It would be important to point out the direction of systemic training of executive functions, that is, the implementation of training within the school system in the form of significant support for the child's development (Sala and Gobet, 2020).

To reduce the risk of mental disorders, children should be provided with executive functions training, which usually includes behavioural, movement-based and mindfulness training methods. Behavioural training can effectively help children with attention deficiency. Movement-based training is supposed to strengthen children's muscles, in particular the brain development, and enhance children's inhibitory control and attention. Mindfulness training aims at removing judgmental experiences at a given moment in terms of feelings, thoughts, and behaviours. It can reduce stress and anxiety, as well as improve children's cognitive control (Qi, 2023).

Psychosocial development of preadolescents

The psychosocial development of preadolescents takes place on several levels and is manifested through certain developmental laws (von Tetzchner, 2022).

This period is characterized by higher emotional vulnerability and more intense emotions. In connection with increased emotional sensitivity, there is also an increased vulnerability to reacting negatively to rejection by peers and the level of conformity increases. In early adolescence, the intensive development of self-awareness and the distinction between the public and private self begins (von Tetzchner, 2022).

Rankin et al. (2004) explain that younger adolescents are more self-confident about their public selves than older adolescents, because younger people have less developed self-reflection skills.

Even in childhood, an inner awareness of what a child would like to be (ideal self) and the associated positive or negative self-evaluation begin to develop. Self-perception is a dynamic mechanism and changes over time, but researchers find that it remains consistent to a certain extent (if a preadolescent is evaluated negatively, there is a high probability that this way of evaluation will be carried with him into adulthood) (Chung et al., 2017).

Erik Erikson, a psychologist and psychoanalyst, developed the theory of psychosocial development in the fifties of the last century, which presents a multi-phase lifelong development theory, including biological, sociological and psychological factors. Each phase includes a developmental task or conflict, which can be resolved successfully or unsuccessfully by the individual. According to Erikson, the period of preadolescence encompasses two developmental states, diligence versus inferiority (5-12) and identity versus identity confusion (13-19) (Orenstein & Lewis, 2022). The developmental crisis that occurs during early adolescence is associated with a reduced loss of identification with parents and an increase in the importance of other social relationships in finding one's place in the wider social context. Erikson (1968, cited in Arnett, 2015) sees the importance of the period of preadolescence, and even more so adolescence, in the transition from a safe environment in the primary family to the development of independence.

In Erikson's theory, a positive transition through the social crisis of the fifth phase leads to a mature identity, whereas a suboptimal transition leads to role confusion and uncertainty about one's identity. The theory is deeply rooted in the social and historical context of Erikson's time, and neo-Eriksonians have revised the theory in various ways and adapted it to today's social reality (von Tetzchner, 2022).

The implications of the psychosocial development of adolescents for their attitude and behaviour towards the internet and social media

Considering the characteristics of the development of preadolescents, this group seems to be particularly at risk of experiencing the negative consequences of online violence. This is mainly influenced by less developed impulse control skills, sensitivity to reward, which increases with excessive use of social networks (also in terms of cognitive changes), and a decrease in the ability to plan long-term (Cohen-Almagor, 2018). Since this is the period of identity development, preadolescents are also more sensitive to pressures from the environment and peers. During this period, children need more excitement, which, on the other hand, means that they are ready to take more risks and go further, i.e. expose and endanger themselves more than individuals in other developmental periods.

Cyberbullying can have lasting effects on preadolescents. Researchers pay a lot of attention to the area of consequences of online violence. The most common symptoms pointed out by many researchers in the field of mental health (Baruah et al., 2017; Han et al., 2021; John et al., 2018; Santos et al., 2021; Vaillancourt et al., 2017) are low self-esteem, elevated levels of anxiety, problems with depression and consequently higher suicidality among the studied population.

Conclusions

Preadolescents are a very vulnerable population due to their developmental characteristics. Preadolescence is a period of accelerated cognitive development. According to Piaget, during this

period the child develops the ability to abstract and deductive and inductive thinking. According to the works of Vygotsky, his cognitive development is heavily influenced by environmental and social influences. During this period, the concepts of self-awareness and the ability to empathize also develop rapidly. From the perspective of neuroscience, the period of preadolescence is strongly marked by the development of executive functions and metacognition. Studies prove that cognitive flexibility is a good protective mechanism against the potentially harmful effects of excessive use of social networks during preadolescence, and as such, it would be important to rapidly develop it within school systems. Better awareness of oneself and one's own mental systems and processes could also be considered a successful protective mechanism. Those individuals who have the aforementioned abilities are less vulnerable to the harmful cognitive consequences of using networks, which can be roughly summed up in damage to attention systems, memory, social cognition, and the reward system in the brain.

In a psychosocial sense, preadolescents are characterized by higher emotional vulnerability and greater intensity of emotions. Peers gain importance during this period, and the fear of social rejection increases. The development of identity becomes important, which is manifested as a successful identity in a mature identity, and as an unsuccessful one in confusion about one's own self. In preadolescence, thrill-seeking and willingness to take risks increase. Due to all the mentioned characteristics, preadolescents are more vulnerable to all forms of online violence. Online violence can mark them in the long term in terms of lowered self-esteem, higher levels of anxiety, depression and risk of suicide.

Although social networks have many positive consequences, it is necessary to protect vulnerable groups of individuals from possible negative outcomes, which are increasingly common due to the increase in the use and exponential development of social networks and poor regulation.

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1.2. Media and Digital Literacy of (Pre)Adolescents

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Why does (media) literacy matter?

Today's children "live mediatized childhoods, and it is no longer possible to contemplate children's social and cultural worlds without considering the role played by the media" (Pereira, 2013, according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019, p. 84), especially by new digital media (Elea & Miklos, 2017 according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019, p. 84). The fact is that the media have an enormous impact on societies and people's lives, which is why there is considerable concern about the impact of digital technologies not only on children's lives but also on the everyday lives of families (González Gaitano, 2008).

"Digital media have become a pervasive component of children's lives in contemporary Western societies: children grow up in a convergent media ecology (Mascheroni & Pasquali, 2013, according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019, p. 84), whereby a variety of everyday practices – self-expression, sociability, learning, games, cultural consumption – take place. Furthermore, the authors claim that contrary to what is argued by media panics-inspired positions, "children are integrating the online and the offline" (Livingstone, 2009, according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019, p. 84) in seeking to develop a coherent projection of the self, but the new digital environment raises new questions because "the information era has brought about new literacies" (Torres, Mercado, 2006, p. 260), and one of the essential literacies in the 21st century in our digital societies is critical digital media literacy, which includes not only the possibility of having access to the media but also – even to a significantly greater extent – the capacity to analyse, to evaluate and to create media contents (Nascimbeni & Vosloo, 2019; Buckingham, 2005 according to Ciboci, Labaš, 2019, p. 84).

As Renee Hobbs writes, the concept of literacy has been expanding for over 2.000 years, adding that "the terms visual literacy, information literacy, and media literacy developed as educators, scholars, artists, and librarians all recognized the need for new skills that mapped onto the changes in society that are reshaping the business, communication, and information landscape" (Hobbs, 2017, p. 5). Divina Frau Meigs states: "Since the advent of Web 2.0, Media and Information Literacy (MIL) is facing a new mutation, as interactivity and the Internet of Things create a sense of augmentation of online activities, and as the industrial lobbies pressure governments in favour of computer literacy. This pressure is not problematic per se but implies the digital affordances as they affect information under its various definitions (code, data, document, news)" (Frau-Meigs, 2015; according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019, p. 84).

Today scholars often research digital literacy (Bell et al., 2022; Scolari et al., 2022; Francis et al., 2021; Hernández-Martín et al., 2021; De la Fuente Prieto et al., 2019; Powers, 2017; Cortoni, 2016; Eleá, 2015; Jones et al., 2015; Koutsogiannis & Adampa, 2012; Calvani et al., 2012; Livingstone, 2011; Knobel & Lankshear, 2006; Ba et al., 2002; Aufderheide & Firestone, 1992) which is, according to Hobbs, "constellation of knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary for thriving in a technology-saturated culture" (Hobbs, 2017, p. 6). People of all ages nowadays need the ability to access, analyse, create, reflect, and take action using various digital tools, forms of expression, and communication strategies (Hobbs, 2017). However, there is a need to care for the well-being of children – preadolescents, and adolescents. "Child digital well-being includes several domains starting from the following: (1)

availability of the Internet, devices and digital competence to use devices and tools; (2) the Internet as an educational tool and platform for accessible and inclusive education; (3) the online environment as a place to socialize with friends and peers and other people and spend structured and unstructured leisure time; and (4) a tool for digital services and specific interventions available to the broader public as well as specific populations. However, the most important prerequisite for achieving and maintaining the digital well-being of children is to be safe from violence, cyberbullying, harassment, abuse, harmful content, fraud, deception, and online exploitation" (Vejmelka et al., 2022, p. 586). Livingstone and O'Neill (2014) argue that online spaces for children and young people should be designed in harmony with children's (also digital) rights - provision, protection, and participation. Is it not even desirable or possible to create a risk-free online space.

The role of the media, its use, and the influence of the media on (pre)adolescents

Various studies have dealt with the role of the media, purposes, and effects of their use in different contexts and life situations (Friesem et al., 2023). "Some studies confirm the positive impact of online communication through social media. For example, in their longitudinal study, Vossen and Valkenburg (2016) point out that adolescents' social media use improved both their ability to understand (cognitive empathy) and share the feelings of their peers (affective empathy). Undoubtedly, the Internet contributes in many ways to realizing children's well-being; however, it is a platform for many risky behaviours and harmful content. Cyberbullying falls under behaviours that are broadly defined by the common name problematic use of the Internet (PUI)" (Vejmelka et al., 2022, p. 586).

According to the author of *Second Self* (1984), *Life on the Screen* (1995), and *Alone Together* (2011) Sherry Turkle, there are more questions about our interpersonal relationships in communication, asking how new media, especially the use of computers, are changing us as people (Turkle, 2011) and why we expect more from technology and less from each other. "She does not agree that computers and new digital devices, such as smartphones, iPods, iPads, and tablets, are 'just tools,' adding that people are shaped by the tools they use. The focus of her research on networking was on the young. However, she also spoke with adults who gave her 'insight into how the network is changing parenting and communications patterns" (Turkle, 2011, according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019, p. 85).

Laura Perdeu asserts that "in today's digital world, there seems to be a thin line between technology use and abuse. Many people's Internet habits may seem excessive: sleeping with a smartphone under the pillow, texting one person while having a face-to-face conversation with another or tweeting from a funeral. However, some people cross that thin line even one step further, going from Internet use and abuse to Internet addiction" (according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019, p. 86). In addition to the problems mentioned above, addiction, the problem of obesity, insomnia, hyperactivity, and memory problems (digital dementia, as Manfred Spitzer in 2018 states) are often associated with children's media use. To these effects, one must add the effects of phone addiction by children and young people who are neglecting face-to-face communication and conversations and the loss of privacy by "sharing too much" on social networks and in "virtual life" (Perdeu, 2014, according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019, p. 87).

Conclusions

As presented reflections show, "today's children and adolescents are immersed in both traditional and new forms of digital media. Research on traditional media, such as television, has identified health concerns and negative outcomes that correlate with the duration and content of viewing. Over the

past decade, the use of digital media, including interactive and social media, has grown, and research evidence suggests that these newer media offer both benefits and risks to the health of children and teenagers. Evidence-based benefits identified from digital and social media use include early learning, exposure to new ideas and knowledge, increased opportunities for social contact and support, and new opportunities to access health promotion messages and information. Risks of such media include negative health effects on sleep, attention, and learning; a higher incidence of obesity and depression; exposure to inaccurate, inappropriate, or unsafe content and contacts; and compromised privacy and confidentiality" (Reid Chassiakos et al., 2016).

Research on the role of the media, the purposes of its use, and the influence of the media in the daily life of (pre)adolescents, which we briefly presented, clearly show that they need "digital and media literacy" (Buckingham, 2015; Hobbs, 2010). In this context, Sonia Livingstone and Julian Sefton-Green (2016) state that digital media literacy is a valid educational key for the future of education in schools and families. They write that "some of how digitally networked, convergent technologies have entered people's ordinary lives may facilitate socially progressive change – supporting youth participation and creative and learning opportunities and providing resources designed for disadvantaged groups. At the same time, there is reason to fear that those same technologies are, with perhaps greater force, being actively reinvented by powerful elites to ensure that political and commercial logics dominate. However, in drawing attention to technologies in this way, we emphasize that they gain their meaning through particular practices and contexts of design and use" (Livingstone & Sefton-Green, 2016, according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019, p. 87). Continuing this reflexion, they add that "it is not just digital technologies that make for change between the present and previous generations – many other changes have shaped the possibilities for and influences on young people in recent decades, and these changes have been more thoroughly researched and theorized" (Livingstone & Sefton-Green, 2016, according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019, p. 87) showing "that crucial changes to home and family have affected children's and young people's lives over recent decades" (Livingstone & Sefton-Green, 2016, according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019, p. 87), and that these "large-scale social changes have implications for the private life of families" (Livingstone & Sefton-Green, 2016, according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019, p. 87), of school and of education (Livingstone & Sefton-Green, 2016, according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019). For children, the media offer "rich resources to explore and express their growing independence, as well as to engage in pleasures that were not always favoured by their parents" (Livingstone & Sefton-Green, 2016, according to Ciboci & Labaš, 2019, p. 87), who was concerned about Internet use.

"In this contemporary context, critical digital media literacy is needed and 'founded on the legitimate role of media to serve the public's right to be truly informed' (Torres, Mercado, 2006, p. 260) and to be educated and literate. In fact, in today's digital age, there is no need and no space to discuss a 'generational divide' or gap between 'digital natives' (children) and 'digital immigrants' (parents) because times have changed. We all need to become 'digitally wise' and to be dedicated to digital media literacy in our everyday lives (Mascheroni et al., 2018, p. 9)" (according to Labaš & Ciboci, 2019, pp. 88-89).

If the planned activities and the target group of the ASAP project are taken into account, they should certainly actively contribute to increasing the media and especially digital competencies of preadolescents so that they can walk in the virtual world as safely as possible and use social media

and new technologies for their development and achievements, and avoid as much as possible all potential dangers and threats.

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1.3. Media and Digital Literacy, Online Risks and Socialisation Settings

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Understanding the concept of literacy

According to UNESCO, the understanding of literacy today goes far beyond the conventional idea that it relates to reading, writing and counting skills. It refers to an individual's ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, and communicate “in an increasingly digital, text-mediated, information-rich and fast-changing world” (Unesco, n.d.). It is a lifelong learning process that enables a person to actively engage and participate in the community and society (UNESCO, 2005). As a key aspect of active participation, literacy emerges as a fundamental and priority competence for countries' development.

Over the decades, various concepts of literacy have emerged to include meaning-making practices that imply using digital technologies and media and various forms and contexts of representation (Sang, 2017). Two of them raise particular interest in the field of Communication Sciences. At the base of the idea of media literacy is the importance of promoting an enlightened understanding of the media and the economic and cultural dimension that encompasses them. It then concerns the using, understanding and creating with the media - a set of crucial skills for the exercise of an active, full citizenship that avoids or reduces the risks of exclusion from community life (European Commission Recommendation 2009/625/EC). Digital literacy in turn focuses on the ability to access, manage, understand, integrate, communicate, evaluate and create information safely and appropriately through digital technologies for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship (Unesco, n.d.). Both ideas intersect and complement each other: while media literacy is a holistic approach to media and to the way it can influence people's perceptions of reality, taught through critical thinking and analysis, digital literacy takes a particular interest in how to use digital media and platforms and in the way they interact with society. Despite their differences, both concern literacy as a matter of empowerment and liberation that enables citizens to live more comfortable lives with less risk of exclusion and poverty (Unesco, n.d.). Thus, given the deeply mediatised context marked by the growth and penetration of digital media in all contexts of our lives, the Braga Declaration (2011) stresses that media literacy is a comprehensive concept and a competence of great importance for all age groups - alongside reading, writing and arithmetic, media literacy is about critically using, understanding and creating images, sounds, and information through various networks and forms of digital and interactive communication.

When it comes to younger people, it is particularly relevant as it is both a matter of empowerment and a matter of protection (Livingstone, 2008; Hobbs & Jensen, 2009). Aged between 7 to 13, pre-teens were born in an age of internet liberalisation and easy access to digital media. Even though social media platforms have established a minimum user age of 13 years, it is frequent for children of younger ages to have profiles and use social networks (Castro, 2015; Rebelo et al., 2020). Particularly since 2019, and because of the pandemic context, media use has grown around 17% (Rideout et al., 2022). The report “The Common Sense Census: Media Use by Tweens and Teens” (Rideout et al., 2022) points out that big increases were noted between 2019 and 2021 in the time spent watching videos online, using social media and browsing websites – digital media became the place to access school,

but also to communicate with family and keep in touch with the peer groups and friends, sometimes with conflicts arising in the digital sphere (Ponte et al., 2021). While Common Sense Media's report warns that there are marked disparities between individuals from lower-income communities and peers from higher-income households in terms of access and consumption - children from lower-income communities tend to access more and spend more time on screens than the others. Though one aspect is transversal to all of them: watching videos online - mostly on YouTube - is the favourite activity of tweens³ regardless of gender, race or ethnic group. In Microsoft's 2023 Global Online Survey on Safety to capture parents and children's perceptions of online safety, general results highlight that 69% teenagers' (aged 13-17) experienced online risk in the past year, however parents seem to underestimate this exposure. The single most prevalent risk reported was misinformation or disinformation (51%), followed closely by personal risks (45%). One-quarter report sexual risks, with child sexual exploitation and abuse the least reported risk (9%). In the case of cyberbullying, harassment or abuse, parents of younger children (6-12) reported higher levels of risk (21%) than parents of teens 13-17 (17%).

These aspects raise attention for the importance of not only empowering young people to use the media safely, but also of helping them to make critical readings of the information conveyed. If, on the one hand, independent use points to the ease and confidence of young people in the face of digital media, on the other hand, it draws attention to the need for a more attentive and careful look on the part of adults. Young children are occasionally seen as "experts" or "pioneers" (Livingstone, 2009), while there are sensitive areas in which these age groups require particular attention and monitoring - e.g. cyber safety and privacy, hate speech and violent content with socio-emotional impact. De Leyn et al. (2021) suggest they navigate between the status of skilled or vulnerable media users. However, and as several works have been pointing out (Selwyn, 2004; Lupton & Williamson, 2017), being able to access the media is not in itself a guarantee that the use will be enlightened and critical. As Selwyn (2004) alerts, to have a truly and enriching digital experience, users need access to digital tools, as well as to know how to effectively use them - something that is not transversal to all children in the world. In Portugal, for instance, during the pandemics the taken-for-granted idea that all children have access to the internet was also shaken.

Nevertheless, we cannot overlook that socio-cultural shifts across the past decades were accommodated in new forms of families, recognised as sites of democratic relationships, stability and security for a child's growth and development, in which the child became a figure with recognised agency and voice (Oswell, 2013). Besides the transformation of intimacy, power dynamics and the rearrangement of the household environment, the connections, relations, and interactions of family members became increasingly mediated and moulded not only by words but by objects too, in which screens are intertwined (Oswell, 2013). Thus, digital media became part of the performing family, "with all its contradictions, conflicts, etc." (Couldry & Hepp, 2017, p. 70). They are part of families coordinated practices through every day (inter)actions (e.g. family conversations occurring while watching TV or speaking with relatives through WhatsApp) and characterise a specific way of "doing

³ According to Common Sense Media, tweens are individuals aged between 8-12 years old.

family” (Morgan, 2011) in late modernity. In line with this, families are simultaneously creators and mediators of children's media consumption (Nathanson, 2015).

At the same time, and if we look at school as a space of free and democratic access (in some cases, the first step of digital inclusion for children and young people) and a privileged place to empower individuals with key competencies and citizenship values (Oliveira, 2022), it will be essential that Media and Digital Education related topics are also addressed in its context. With the profound socio-technological changes experienced in the last three decades, it has been pointed out an urgent need to adapt both the school context and the pedagogical practices. According to Gutiérrez and Tyner, schools cannot ignore social and cultural developments – by doing so they run the risk of training young people to be citizens in a society that no longer exists (2012, p. 2). They also emphasise that the digitalisation of information, the importance of social networks and digital media, and even multiculturalism, are subjects that are little addressed in school, causing a gap between the reality experienced and what is learned in the classroom (Gutiérrez & Tyner, 2012). This gap goes even further if we ignore the importance that informal learning contexts have in the development of the younger generations and the ways in which they learn (Amiama-Espailat & Mayor-Ruiz, 2017; Andersen et al., 2020; Cruz & Díaz, 2016; Pérez-Escoda et. al, 2016; Seemiller & Grace, 2019).

In the Portuguese context, for instance, particular interest has risen in the issue of teacher media and digital competencies and the importance of teacher development to positively impact the students' learning experience. Though several guide documents and strategies have been developed intending to guide teaching practice and propose guidelines to promote digital and media competencies in the context of formal education - namely the Media Education Guidance, the Citizenship Education National Strategy, among others - teachers still make little use of these materials to support their teaching and to promote innovation in the classroom (Oliveira, 2022).

Conclusion

The data presented in this section reinforce the idea that the growing use and integration of digital media in the daily routines of younger age groups (including preadolescents) has contributed to an increasing involvement in online risk situations. Though risk is an important part of growing up, it is fundamental that young children, and - in the scope of this project - pre-teens, learn to deal with dangerous situations, learning from mistakes and knowing who to turn to in dangerous situations. The widespread idea that youngsters are digital natives⁴, naturally born with inherent digital skills promotes a lack of attention towards the urgency of focusing on sensitive areas - such as cyber safety and privacy, hate speech and violent content with socio-emotional impact -, working not only with youngsters but also with adults with educational responsibilities in their lives.

⁴ The idea of “digital natives” refers to individuals who have grown up surrounded by digital technology (e.g. computers, the internet, and mobile devices) and are assumed to be naturally adept at using these tools. The concept is attributed to Marc Prensky in 2001, who argued that young people immersed in digital environments from birth think and learn differently from previous generations of “digital immigrants”. However, a significant amount of research has shown that the concept is oversimplified and that there are several other characteristics and criteria besides age that dictate the relationship between individuals and the media, including their predisposition to use it.

In line with the objectives of the ASAP project, the data formerly mentioned highlight two central aspects: 1) on the one hand, the important of paying attention to the pedagogical practices adopted in formal settings, and to the skills, competencies and experiences of informal learning settings; 2) on the other, of addressing a wide range of audiences - from pre-teens to teachers and families -, in order to bring these groups together and work to promote cross-cutting skills, cooperation and mutual growth.

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1.4. Understanding Social Media Analysis Within Social Science

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Introduction

Social media has become a significant research topic within the social sciences, allowing for interdisciplinary studies between media and communication studies and fields like anthropology.

This first section provides an overview of the relationship between social media and social science, highlighting the need for research on social media usage among preadolescents and its impact on the development of digital skills in preadolescents and adolescents. It discusses the importance of avoiding generalisations and considering diverse social groups and contexts in social media analysis. The text further explores anthropological perspectives on the theory of attainment, mediatisation, and the concept of affordance in relation to social media. By synthesising these interdisciplinary perspectives, this text contributes to the broader discourse on social media and its implications for social science research. It highlights the need for nuanced examinations of social media usage, especially among younger demographics, to comprehend the evolving digital landscape better and to inform policies and interventions that promote positive digital engagement and well-being among kids.

Social media and social science

Anthropologists and social scientists have extensively researched the relationship between media and social change since the 1980s. Studies in these fields often examine specific media forms and practices within the context of broader societal or regional changes, aiming to understand new social "rituals" and networking relationships. For instance, the impact of mobile technology has been explored as a catalyst for social dynamism in various parts of the world, particularly in the Global South, and highlighting the importance of addressing people's aspirations for societal change and the potential revitalization of traditional cultural forms, such as kin-based reciprocity also through the use of media (e.g., Postill, 2017).

In recent years, the widespread use of the Internet and the emergence of online platforms like YouTube, Snapchat, WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram have made "social media " a significant research topic across various disciplines within social science. The analysis of social media has created an opportunity for media and communication studies to intersect with other social sciences, including anthropology and sociology.

For anthropologists, the study of the scalable nature of online platforms is particularly intriguing, as the analysis of sociality and social changes is at the core of their field. In addition, there are several other topics that garner considerable interest within social science studies, including the examination of user behaviours, practices, and perceptions on social media platforms, the role of algorithms and codes, identity and self-representation online, the impact of anonymity, the role of social media in

activism and politics, to name a few⁵. Most of these studies are at the intersection of media and communication investigation and social sciences.

There is however a lack of research on social media usage and its impact on the development of digital skills in preadolescents (and adolescents) that is an interest of the ASAP project. Particularly when it comes to qualitative observations of everyday life and health promotion and habits, limited or no studies have been conducted in this area, as indicated by the existing literature.

When it comes to studying social media use among youth, particularly adolescents, one notable anthropological study is Danah Boyd's book, "It's Complicated: The Social Lives of Networked Teens," published by Yale University Press (2014). Her book examines how American teenagers use social media platforms and the impact these platforms have on their relationships and identities. The book challenges common assumptions about teenagers and their online behaviours, promoting a more nuanced understanding of their experiences. For instance, Boyd explores how teenagers manage their online privacy and negotiate the tension between sharing personal information and maintaining control over their digital identities. She also explores how online interactions allow teens to experiment with different aspects of their identity and connect with like-minded individuals. Regarding parental concerns, she emphasises the importance of understanding teenagers' online experiences and highlights the generational gap that can lead to misunderstandings and misinterpretations of their online behaviour.

She also explores how social media use among teens reflects and reinforces existing social inequalities. Boyd discusses how socioeconomic factors influence teenagers' online experiences and shape their digital literacy skills. The book explores the concept of digital inequality and how it impacts teenagers' access to and use of technology.

While various studies have examined children's activities on specific popular platforms like YouTube, this significant study by Lange stands out (Lange, 2014). Lange's research is a two-year ethnographic study that delves into the experiences of kids on YouTube during its early days, from 2006 to 2008, when the platform was first launched. This study by Lange is relevant to the ASAP project as it moves beyond the "narcissistic" analysis of self-centeredness associated with video content creators or YouTubers, instead highlighting the opportunities for children to acquire technical, personal, and social skills through their participation on the social media platform. Both studies by Boyd (2014) and Lange (2014) can provide valuable insights for the ASAP project regarding their methodological approaches, conclusions, and recommendations. However, it is important to note that while these studies may offer helpful guidance, the project should also consider suggestions from anthropological and sociological research conducted on social media that may not directly target the specific audience or focus of the project. This broader range of studies can provide additional perspectives and insights that may apply to the project's objectives.

Avoiding generalisation: anthropological perspectives

The criticism of generalising across various groups on social media in media studies has been a recurring topic (Miller et al., 2016; Postill, 2017). Postill argues that it is erroneous to generalise across

⁵ For further references, see journals such as *Social Media + Society*; *Media, Culture & Society*.

different social groups and time periods when investigating media uses, emphasising the importance of taking a diachronic approach and the social changes they bring about (Postill, 2017). Miller et al. (2016) also caution against the risks of generalisation in many media studies. In their work "How the World Changed Social Media," these authors express their concerns, stating that:

“Most studies of the internet and social media are based on research methods that assume we can generalise across different groups. We look at tweets in one place and write about ‘Twitter’. We conduct tests about social media and friendship in one population and then write on this topic as if friendship means the same thing for all populations.” (Miller et al. 2016, p. V).

To address this concern, it is recommended that ASAP project future research and activities consider the diverse social groups and contexts in which social media is used. This could involve employing a diachronic approach that examines changes over time and acknowledges the nuances within different populations, contexts, or countries. Partners should be mindful of the potential limitations and biases that arise from assuming universal patterns across social media usage. By embracing a more comprehensive understanding of diverse social groups, future studies can provide a richer and more accurate portrayal of the complex relationship between (digital) media and society.

Theory of attainment: anthropological perspectives

Miller and Sinanan (2014) have contributed to the field of anthropology by developing the "theory of attainment," which challenges the popular assumption that digital technologies fundamentally change what it means to be human. Instead, they argue that technologies like webcams facilitate new ways of being human, fulfilling our innate aspirations for communication beyond immediate surroundings, much like other historical inventions such as pens, phones, and email. This theory emphasises the co-evolution of humans and technology, highlighting the mutually constitutive nature of their relationship.

In a more recent publication, Daniel Miller et al. (2016) discuss the common pattern of moral panic and polarised views surrounding new technologies, including social media platforms. They note that there is often a fear that face-to-face communication is being compromised or that cognitive abilities like long-term attention spans are being lost. These concerns echo historical reactions to technological advancements, such as Plato's belief that the invention of writing would harm our memory. Conversely, there are also utopian perspectives that view new technologies as transformative, potentially making us post-human in some way (Miller et al., 2016, p. 6).

These insights shed light on the ongoing debates and diverse interpretations surrounding the impact of digital technologies on human communication and cognition. They invite ASAP partners to consider the nuanced dynamics between technology and humanity, challenging both dystopian and utopian narratives and encouraging a more balanced and contextual understanding of their coexistence.

Mediatisation and the concept of affordance: anthropological perspectives

The reliance on media has been studied within media and communication studies and social science disciplines. Researchers aim to understand how media are integrated into everyday life, shaping our actions and influencing our understanding of the social world.

Jansson's study (2014) is often referenced by researchers to explain the concept of reliance on digital media in our daily lives. It is seen as a key indicator of mediatisation wherein our lives become increasingly dependent on and adapted to media (Jansson, 2014, 2018) (cited in Bengtsson et al., 2020, pp. 276). Andersen further suggests that everyday activities are influenced by the omnipresence of media or specific forms of communication. In this regard, the theory of mediatisation provides a framework for understanding social and cultural change in terms of how media become embedded in specific practices (Andersen, 2018).

The notion of deep mediatisation emphasises the growing dependence of many social processes on communication infrastructures (Couldry & Hepp, 2016, p. 37, cited in Andersen, 2018). This concept highlights the increasing influence and integration of media into various aspects of society.

When it comes to social media platforms, their pervasive presence in our daily lives is accompanied by numerous technical elements such as codes and algorithms.

These elements possess a certain degree of agency, intersecting with and even influencing human actions and choices. Andersen argues that search engines, algorithms, and databases themselves can be seen as manifestations of "deep mediatisation" (Andersen, 2018). These technological elements influence our ordinary activities through practices of ordering, searching, archiving, and filtering.

As we appropriate them for our own purposes or interact with them in our everyday lives, their underlying ideology contributes to potential changes in how we engage with the world (Andersen, 2018, pp. 2). Algorithms, for example, can operate independently of human control, adding complexity to the agency and mediatisation of social media (Kitchin & Dodge, 2011, cited in Curlew, 2019).

Bengtsson et al. (2020) have raised important research questions, such as how digital media saturation affects individuals' lives and to what extent different groups perceive their lives as dependent on media. Understanding the power dynamics of social media platforms requires capturing users' personal perspectives, including their intuitive, affective, and experiential knowledge, through the concept of "affordances" (Swart, 2021).

The concept of affordances is particularly relevant when studying social media among preadolescents, as it allows for an intuitive and multi-sited exploration of the platform's effects. Affordances of social media refer to how platforms silently mediate interactions, influencing behaviours and shaping consequences (Bonini et al., 2023, Curlew, 2019).

It highlights the inherent capabilities and potentials of the social media platform, ultimately impacting the world as demonstrated by the influence of Facebook and Twitter for instance on political polarisations (Miller's interview, 2015, cited in Borgerson and Miller, 2016, pp. 521).

Conclusion

This chapter highlights the need for more research on social media usage among preadolescents and its impact on digital skills development. It emphasises the importance of avoiding generalisations and considering diverse social groups and contexts in social media analysis. By embracing a more comprehensive understanding of diverse social groups, project activities can provide a richer and more accurate portrayal of the complex relationship between (digital) media and target groups. This approach promotes inclusivity and avoids the perpetuation of stereotypes or assumptions about preadolescents' digital behaviour. It encourages a more comprehensive understanding of their

experiences, challenges, and aspirations, leading to more relevant and engaging digital skills education programmes. Ultimately, by avoiding generalisations, digital skills education programmes can better serve the needs of preadolescents, their families, and school communities. This approach allows for tailored methods that empower preadolescents to navigate the digital world confidently, critically, and responsibly, fostering their digital well-being and preparing them for the opportunities and challenges of the digital age.

So, to effectively support preadolescents in the digital age, it is crucial to delve into their experiences, challenges, and aspirations. Consider the agency of digital platform, and the importance they are gaining in everyday lives. This understanding will aid in creating relevant and engaging digital skills education programmes that cater to their needs.

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1.5. Marketing Perspective on Social Media

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Today, social media is counted as one of the most important parts of marketing strategies, which has led to a paradigm change in this field. Social media marketing has been growing over the recent years and is predicted to be exponentially growing in the future (Pour et al., 2021).

Before we begin exploring social media marketing, it is critical to define and comprehend the term "social media". Social media are communication tools that incorporate Web 2.0 features such as participation, collaboration, knowledge dissemination, and user empowerment (Kargaran et al., 2017). There is no universally accepted definition of Web 2.0. It is referred to as the web's next generation, with more mature communication platforms and user-centred web applications. It has features such as collaboration, social connectedness, knowledge sharing, user-generated content, and it is free (Pour et al., 2020). Among the advantages of social media marketing are increased access, increased traffic, increased loyal customers, improved market insights, improved search ranking, expanded business partnerships, more intellectual leadership, improved sales, and lower marketing costs. Because of the growing popularity of social networking sites like Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter, there has been an increase in social commerce and social media marketing (Akman & Mishra, 2017).

Weblogs, social blogs, microblogs, wikis, podcasts, photos, videos, and social bookmarking are some examples of social media. When their use grows rapidly, not only established social networks, but also businesses and public organizations, will benefit. In contrast to individual social networkers, these organizations actively use media for advertising and marketing. Commercial communications and consumer interactions with media, events, entertainment, retailers, and the digital network can be carried out at a much lower cost and effort than previously (Guha et al., 2021).

In this chapter, we are mainly focusing 1) on the role of social media from the marketing perspective (advertisers, communicators), especially in targeting adolescents and preadolescents, 2) on the role of influencers in producing the content on social media for the purpose of marketing (advertising) and increasing sales revenues and 3) on the behaviour and attitudes of (pre)adolescents towards influencers and the marketing content on social media.

The role of social media from the marketing perspective

Social media marketing is the use of social media technologies, channels, and software to create, communicate, deliver, and exchange value-added offerings for an organization's stakeholders (Tuten & Solomon, 2017).

In recent years, the use of social media platforms as marketing channels has increased to disseminate brand-related content and engage with customers and their conversations. It has emerged as the most important digital marketing channel, with marketing executives widely accepting and expanding its use (Iankova et al., 2019). Given the importance of social media in customers' online activities, social media marketing has emerged as a dominant strategy in digital marketing plans. Social media has altered the way businesses interact with their customers to promote their products or services (Janavi et al., 2021). According to Arya et al. (2018), companies integrate their system with social media while

developing their marketing strategy to improve the quality of real-time interaction with consumers. As a result, the use of social media platforms is at the top of marketers' priorities to effectively communicate with customers, gather customer knowledge and feedback on the company's products and services, build a reputation, and increase sales (Jami Pour & Jafari, 2019). This has transformed consumers from being silent, remotely unreachable, and invisible individuals to becoming lively, socially dynamic, and even more collective individuals (Arya et al., 2019).

Social media marketing enables businesses to develop and manage many relationships relatively easily (Arnone & Deprince, 2016) and to strengthen existing relationships (Almeida & Santos, 2020). Direct interaction with customers all over the world provides the opportunity to form long-lasting, emotional bonds (Fleischmann & Fleischmann, 2019). Prior research also shows that social media can be used effectively to gather market information for marketing purposes (Almeida & Santos, 2020).

While scholars generally agree that social media reduces marketing costs and that setting up social media is usually free and with reasonable media spending, digital content must be appealing, and the ever-increasing number of followers necessitates qualified resources to respond to their posts. Even though starting a social media campaign is inexpensive, businesses still require employees with IT and communication skills. Each social media platform is unique, requiring time-consuming following and posting, resulting in increased content management costs (Almeida & Santos, 2020).

With the advent of social media, businesses now have new ways to reach out to their customers. Even within social media platforms, various forms of marketing exist. One constant across all forms of marketing, however, is the need for engagement. Previously, marketing was more concerned with impressions, or the number of people who saw the advertisement; however, the need for engagement has now taken precedence. "...when using social media, you want to "engage" your audience by offering promotions, contests, content, articles, video, and so on. Whatever it takes to get people talking to, about, and with you" (Kelsey & Lyon, 2017).

This simplified definition of viral aids businesses in understanding the importance of engaging an audience and encouraging them to share campaigns through "network-enhanced word-of-mouth." When their content is shared, the fact that certain demographics share likes and dislikes could certainly benefit these companies' social media marketing. A strong social media presence, on the other hand, can bring a company thousands of fans as well as thousands of detractors (Azpeitia, 2021).

Customer engagement is a two-way street. As a result, it is critical that businesses create interactive social media accounts that satisfy customers with quick responses. Even when confronted with criticism, responsive businesses can maintain positive relationships with their target audiences as long as they address the issues at hand rather than remaining silent and hoping the problems will resolve themselves (Azpeitia, 2021).

The role of influencers

The origin of the concept of influencers can be traced to traditional media and the presence of opinion leaders who lead discussions on specific topics related to their expertise for the purpose of persuasion (Zhao et al., 2018). If we extend this definition to the field of social media, we can say that influencers are users who began as regular people or are famous in a field and have a large number of followers on one or more online media platforms (e.g., Instagram, TikTok, YouTube) and frequently persuade followers through their authentic messages (Lou & Yuan, 2019). The stars of social media are vloggers

on YouTube, which have become important influencers for the purchase decision of their young audiences. They give their fans and followers an insight into their daily lives, and which brands they prefer and which they don't (Veirman et al., 2019).

Influencer marketing is a type of social media marketing in which brands use social media influencers to drive brand recognition, conduct product placements, and endorse products on their individual social media pages to boost purchase intentions of that brand among their consumers or the followers of the social media influencers (Lou & Yuan, 2019).

Influencer marketing has grown in popularity over the years and is now a marketing buzzword. In 2018, influencer marketing was a 4.6-billion-dollar industry, and that figure is expected to rise even further in the future. Influencer marketing is thought to have an eight-fold higher return on investment than more traditional forms of paid advertising (Influencer Marketing Hub, 2019). Although traditional advertising and influencer marketing have some similarities, the latter can be regarded as a disruptive evolution in marketing for a variety of reasons. Social media influencers interact with their followers and provide a new marketing strategy that is perceived as interactive and authentic (Lou & Yuan, 2019). Moreover, viewers and followers identify with influencers as the impactful girls or guys next door and, as a result, view influencers as credible sources of information. For example, in contrast to inaccessible traditional celebrities, influencers engage in direct conversations with and connect with their followers through their social media. Furthermore, influencers frequently establish themselves as experts in specific domains, increasing their credibility as product promotion sources in the eyes of their followers (Balaban & Mustăţea, 2019).

Social media platforms like Facebook and Instagram encourage users to interact by liking and/or commenting on other people's posts. Such interactions tend to strengthen users' social bonds and increase their attachment and emotional belonging to the community (Zeng et al., 2017). Users do this not only for posts from family and friends, but also for posts from unrelated influencers. In other words, influence occurs when a child or adult user watches/reads, likes, comments/interacts with a social media influencer on a sponsored brand post posted by that individual, utilizing their social capital (van Dam & van Reijmersdal, 2019). Social bonds are formed because of interactions with influencers, and users become more receptive to user-relevant product endorsements from social influencers (Zeng et al., 2017). Adolescents frequently form strong bonds with influencers, and those "with whom you have strong relationships are usually not expected to have ulterior motives" (van Dam & van Reijmersdal, 2019, p. 2). As a result, social media influencers can be regarded as social agents influencing an adolescent's consumer socialization process (Meng-Hsien et al., 2019).

In contrast to traditional advertisements, product endorsements or brand messages posted by social media influencers appear as personal status updates, seamlessly promoting the brand as if it were a personal recommendation from a friend or family member. Personal recommendations are treated differently by users than advertisements, and they tend to have a more positive brand effect on the users (De Jans et al., 2018).

Almost all marketers, including business-to-business brands, are starting to use social media influencers because the return on investment is substantially higher than that of traditional media (Ahmad, 2018). Furthermore, a great number of marketers who have used social media influencers to spread their brand message believe in its effectiveness (Folkvord et al., 2019). According to surveys, users tend to buy more based on the recommendations of influencers (Lou & Yuan, 2019).

Influencer marketing, even if celebrities are hired, is often less expensive than mass media advertisements. Furthermore, unlike a standardized message on TV or print, the brand message can be easily personalized and varied from one influencer to the next. This enables brands to adapt to various target markets and demographic profiles, as well as geographic locations and local cultures, resulting in a win-win situation for brands and firms. In an age when consumers opt out of ads and use AdBlock on websites, the most significant advantage for brands using influencer marketing is that users choose to follow social media influencers and are thus more open to engaging with the influencer's posts. Furthermore, around 30% of 12-17-year-olds cannot recognize influencer advertising on social media and are unaware that influencers receive compensation from the company in exchange for their endorsement, leading them to mistake a sponsored brand message for a personal recommendation (Ofcom, 2023).

The behaviour and attitude of (pre)adolescents

Adolescents' use of social media has become especially habitual, which means they are constantly exposed to native advertisements (Lou & Yuan, 2019). Influencer posts are a type of native advertising because the commercial intent is hidden behind a personal message curated by the social media influencer (van Dam & van Reijmersdal, 2019).

Influencers appear to be highly influential and affect young children's brand preferences. Given their limited skills in understanding advertisements and critical evaluation of advertisements, children under the age of 12 are a vulnerable target group (Veirman et al., 2019). The ease with which children and adolescents can follow the updates of social media influencers has been aided by the widespread availability of social media on mobile devices such as smartphones (Anderson & Jiang, 2018). According to the Italian National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT) Report from 2021, over 59% of adolescents use a smartphone daily and 46% of them use it for more than 3 hours per day. They use it for the following purposes: internet (59%), consulting social media (72% Instagram; 62% TikTok and 58% YouTube) (Bozzola, et al., 2022). As a result, for many adolescents, watching videos by social media influencers has become far more essential than watching traditional television programs (Smit et al., 2019).

Moreover, algorithms choose automatic recommendations that appear alongside the clip viewers are currently watching (Smith et al., 2018). This constant flow of new information is likely to provoke the feeling of missing out on something important, also known as FOMO (the fear of missing out) which early adolescents (between 10 and 14 years of age) are particularly prone to experience (Schmuck, 2021).

It is suggested that adolescents tend to find influencers as those who are more relatable and credible, as they often aspire to be like them. They regard these influencer messages as more trustworthy and honest than other commercial messages (De Jans et al., 2018). Furthermore, because they are often close in age to their audience, the content provided by social media influencers fits their frame of reference (Marôpo et al., 2020).

Lou and Yuan (2019) discover that the trustworthiness of the influencer was the primary driver of purchase intention. They noted that trust in branded posts and educational value, rather than the influencer's attractiveness or entertainment value of the message, were critical in influencing a user's purchase decisions, prompting many brands to reach children through social media influencers.

Conclusion

Today, social networks are considered one of the most important marketing strategies, which has grown exponentially in recent years and is predicted to continue to do so in the future. Social networks are communication tools that involve active user participation and are accessible and widespread. In parallel with the use of social networks, companies are also increasingly using these networks for marketing. Promotion through social networks is becoming the leading strategy of companies' digital marketing plans. Younger generations increasingly use marketing appeals of so-called influencers, who are users of social media who started as regular people or are famous in a field and have many followers on one or more online media platforms. Influencers approach the user in an authentic way, with new ideas and products and present themselves "as one of us" and thereby gaining the user's credibility and trust.

Adolescents and preadolescents massively use social networks and are constantly exposed to the influence of marketing, which is often geared to the specifics of their perception and response. Almost half of adolescents use social networks for several hours a day, and these contents dominate television. The constant algorithmic adaptation of content to their interests and the accelerated flow of information can trigger the so-called fear of missing out (FOMO), which affects even more intensive use. The accelerated growth of the use of social networks and the ever-worsening transparency and control over content raise many concerns about the harmful consequences that excessive use can bring to users.

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1.6. Social Media Addiction: Dopamine and Rewards

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Introduction

Until 2011 only a few research was conducted in the area of social networking and whether excessive use of social media could lead to addiction. Since then, there have been hundreds of studies examining many aspects of social media use, bringing to a growing scientific evidence base that suggests that excessive social media use may lead to symptoms traditionally associated with substance-related addictions.

As we live in a connected world, in which the Internet is not only unavoidable and ubiquitous, but also a highly functional aspect of modern living, these findings brought with them a general preoccupation for people's wellbeing and a particular concern for younger generations, born as digital natives⁶ and brought up entirely in this framework.

Asked to define the danger of social media addiction in adolescents, Mark D. Griffiths, Distinguished Professor of Behavioural Addiction at the International Gaming Research Unit, Psychology Department at Nottingham Trent University, sustains that probably social media addiction regards a small amount of individuals, but he firmly believes that problematic use of social media can bring consequences as intrapsychic conflicts (within the individual often including a subjective loss of control) and interpersonal conflicts (i.e., problems with the immediate social environment, including relationship problems and education being compromised) (Griffiths, 2018).

Social media addiction, problematic social media use and compulsive social media use, are all terms used interchangeably to refer to the phenomenon of maladaptive social media use characterized by either addiction-like symptoms (as dependency) and/or reduced self-regulation (Marino et al., 2018).

Griffiths (2017) defines criteria used for the diagnosis of addiction (as a psychiatric syndrome) to determine the framework of social media addiction:

1. **Salience:** use of social networking sites that may become the most important activity that they engage in, leading to a preoccupation with social networking sites use.
2. **Mood modification:** activities on these sites are then being used to induce mood alterations, pleasurable feelings or a numbing effect.
3. **Tolerance:** increased amounts of time and energy are required to be put into engaging with social networking sites activities to achieve the same feelings and state of mind that occurred in the initial phases of usage.

⁶ The idea of "digital natives" refers to individuals who have grown up surrounded by digital technology (e.g. computers, the internet, and mobile devices) and are assumed to be naturally adept at using these tools. The concept is attributed to Marc Prensky in 2001, who argued that young people immersed in digital environments from birth think and learn differently from previous generations of "digital immigrants". However, a significant amount of research has shown that the concept is oversimplified and that there are several other characteristics and criteria besides age that dictate the relationship between individuals and the media, including their predisposition to use it.

4. Withdrawal: when social networking sites use is discontinued, addicted individuals will experience negative psychological and sometimes physiological symptoms.
5. Relapse: to solve negative psychological and physiological symptoms social networking sites use is reinstated.

Dopamine addiction and driven feedback

Addiction is strictly related to the search for pleasure and happiness, typical in human behaviour. It is defined as a physiological demand for the presence of the substance or a behaviour/experience that helps our brain to find pleasure and happiness in our daily lives.

Social relationships and having a sense of connection are important determinants of happiness and stress relief, mental and physical well-being, and even mortality.

Our motivations towards using social media are broadly similar to the instinctual desires of social interactions to exchange information and ideas, along with gaining social support and friendships (Firth et al, 2019).

Dopamine is a natural neurotransmitter that has numerous important roles in the body and specifically in the brain in which it has many functions including memory, moto-coordination, attention and motivation. Generally, it is seen to be the 'pleasure chemical' because it is connected to the mechanism behind why humans feel pleasure. It is released by the neurons and sends signals to other nerve cells within the central nervous system.

Particularly, dopamine is involved in reward-motivated behaviour (Burhan and Moradzadeh, 2020). Rather than giving pleasure itself, dopamine motivates individuals to do things that might bring them pleasure. They experience a hike in dopamine in anticipation of doing something as well as when doing the thing itself. As soon as the hike is finished, the brain experiences a dopamine dip because of homeostasis, a process of self-regulation to maintain a physiological balance.

During the comedown state, the brain looks for repeating the experience, a necessity that passes unless an addiction is present. For these reasons scientists use dopamine to measure the addictive potential of any experience: the higher the dopamine release is, the more addictive the substance/experience will be (Lembke, 2021).

Regarding social media use, dopamine intervenes in the reward prediction error encoding, a feedback loop related to dopamine feedback signals that can be likened to other forms of addictive behaviour like gambling. Essentially people that spend hours on social media platforms activate the exact mechanism as those who gamble on a machine in a casino, with an intense anticipatory period. At this stage dopamine neurons are very active and then gradually decrease as negative outcomes build up (Burhan and Moradzadeh, 2020).

Furthermore, even when not using the Internet for any specific purpose, smartphones have introduced widespread and habitual "checking" behaviours, characterised by quick but frequent inspections of the device for incoming information from news, social media, or personal contacts. These habits are thought to be the result of behavioural reinforcement from "information rewards" that are received immediately on checking the device, potentially engaging the cortico-striatal dopaminergic system due to their readily available nature (Firth et al, 2019). Behavioural scientists call these addiction-inducing patterns "intermittent reinforcement" or "variable ratio schedules".

Neuroscientists have identified that a cue triggering a behaviour that yields a reward 50% of the time is by far the most anxiety-inducing of delivery schedules. A reward delivered 75% of the time, for example, can be reliably expected to deliver most of the time. A cue signalling a reward that delivers 25% of the time can similarly be expected not to deliver most of the time. (Veissière et al, 2018)

Such high-predictability schedules (when the brain can reliably predict what is going to happen) typically trigger low arousal. At a 50% delivery rate, a reward schedule is still predictable enough to be enticing, but unpredictable enough to be anxiety-inducing. When rewards become most unpredictable, in turn, arousal typically becomes negative, giving rise to anxiety (Veissière et al, 2018).

The possible rewards in social media (getting texts, likes or messages) evoke feelings of happiness and satisfaction due to the “virtual” social life that social media platforms mimic, which is why they can easily keep individuals in the loop. Essentially, that’s how social media apps exploit our innate systems: by users checking their phones for notifications and updates at periodic intervals for something that could be intrinsically rewarding. Most of the time it’s a neutral stimulus, but on occasion there may be a positive stimulus leading to the rewarding dopamine release hence keeping the user in the feedback loop (Burhan and Moradzadeh, 2020).

Anna Lembke, chief of Stanford University’s dual diagnosis addiction clinic, emphasises that the smartphone is the “modern-day hypodermic needle” as we turn to it for “quick hits, seeking attention, validation and distraction with each swipe, like and tweet”. She talks about a turn “from substance to behavioural addiction” with social media stimulating us with every swipe and scroll, filling every available spare time we have. In her opinion, the digital world enables bingeing on a previously unseen scale because there are no practical limitations forcing us to pause as happens with substances: social media are always there, with a little effort.

Also, she adds that obsession with instant gratification means we are constantly living in our limbic brain (which processes emotions) rather than in our pre-frontal cortex (which deals with future planning and problem-solving) mining personality development (Lembke, 2021).

Is social media built to facilitate habitual use?

In previous research, some authors suggested that some individuals may develop addiction-related problems because of their mobile phone use. Recent ones suggested that problematic mobile phone use is connected essentially to the use of specific applications, including calls, instant messaging, and the use of social networks. Smartphones (or tablets) are not addictive per se, but because they are the media that enable the engagement in potentially addictive activities (Griffiths & Nuyens, 2017).

Scholars such as Alter (2017) do not even believe that social media platforms are designed to be addictive per se. Veissière (2018) suggested that it is the social expectations and rewards of connecting with other people and seeking to learn from others that induce and sustain addictive relationships with smartphones. These scholars argue that mobile technology addiction is driven by the human urge to connect with people, and the related necessity to be seen, heard, thought about, guided, and monitored by others, which reaches deep in our social brains and far in our evolutionary past (Veissière, 2018).

However, social media is certainly designed to get users. Their structure and functioning, as a matter of fact, play a central role in habitual use, especially when it comes to adolescents. Some of them concern unpredictable rewards, social affirmation and validation, FOMO (fear of missing out),

smartphone sounds and vibrations, social connection, reciprocal liking, social competition, and psychological investment (Griffiths, 2018).

Unpredictable rewards

As described before, one of the key psychological characteristics in habitual social media use is the unpredictability and randomness of what happens within social media platforms (Griffiths and Nuyens, 2017). The rewards can be infrequent but even the anticipation of one of these rewards can be psychologically and/or physiologically pleasing (Griffiths, 2018).

Social affirmation and validation

Another key ingredient that facilitates habitual social media use is the 'like' button. The feature was first introduced by Facebook back in February 2009. Still such a simple characteristic has reaped huge rewards in terms of adolescents repeatedly coming back to check their social media platforms, and what some have described as a 'craving for validation'. Some media reports have described the use of 'like' buttons as 'hijacking' the social reward systems of a user's brain (Morgans, 2017).

Justin Rosenstein, one of the designers of the 'like' button on Facebook said: "The main intention I had was to make positivity the path of least resistance, and I think it succeeded in its goals, but it also created large unintended negative side effects. In a way, it was too successful" (Morgans, 2017). Although teenagers do not use Facebook as much as other apps, other social media platforms use similar techniques.

Fear of missing out

Recent studies indicate that excessive involvement in social media may stem from a phenomenon referred to as "fear of missing out" (FOMO), a widespread concern that others are having enjoyable experiences one is not a part of.

Higher FOMO levels have been linked to increased usage of Facebook, reduced overall mood, decreased wellbeing, decreased life satisfaction, conflicting emotions when using social media, and inappropriate or risky behaviour on social networking sites (Griffiths & Nuyens, 2017).

Smartphone sounds and vibrations

Rings, pings, buzzes, or vibrations of an incoming message or notification cause a reaction to the stimulus and bring to look at the mobile devices' screens. This creates a routine with individuals always looking at social media feeds, which Morgans says is perfect to match companies' demand for individuals' attention. He said: "The business model is simple: the more attention a platform can pull, the more effective its advertising space becomes, allowing it to charge advertisers more" (Morgans, 2017).

Sounds and vibrations are deliberately designed and distracting technologies that facilitate users' attention away from the offline world and back to life online and is arguably an example of 'persuasive technology' (Alter, 2017). Sean Parker (founding president of Facebook) recently acknowledged that the company was formed to distract individuals rather than unite them. More specifically, he said that Facebook's thought process was simple: "How do we consume as much of your time and conscious attention as possible? [Facebook's architects exploited a] vulnerability in human psychology.

Whenever someone likes or comments on a post or photograph, we give you a little dopamine hit” (Solon, 2017).

Reciprocal liking

Reciprocal liking is the tendency for individuals to like others who express a liking for themselves. Social relationships online are often facilitated by simple forms of social reciprocity (as the “like” button) (Griffiths, 2018). Social media operators can exploit this human condition of reciprocal liking by alerting individuals when another person has read something posted or communicated online. Such alerts encourage the receiving individuals to respond (Griffiths, 2018). In line with the notion of a ‘common neural currency’ of monetary and social reward, giving and receiving Likes — a unique feature of online environments that resembles both social and monetary reward — robustly recruits brain circuitry implicated in other reward tasks (Sherman et al., 2018).

Conclusion

This chapter explores the addictive nature of social media use and its potential impact on well-being. It discusses the role of dopamine and reward mechanisms in driving habitual use and highlights the potential negative consequences, such as intrapsychic and interpersonal conflicts. When it comes to preadolescents and social media usage, their developing brains and socio-emotional processes make them particularly vulnerable to the addictive aspects of social media. Preadolescents may be more susceptible to seeking validation, acceptance, and social connections, which are often gratified through the interactions and feedback on social media platforms. This desire for social validation can drive preadolescents to engage in habitual use and seek the pleasurable feelings associated with dopamine release.

The addiction and dopamine debate highlights the importance of understanding and addressing the potential risks of excessive social media use among preadolescents. It emphasises the need for interventions and strategies that promote healthy digital habits and empower preadolescents to regulate their online behaviour. By raising awareness about the addictive nature of social media and fostering digital literacy skills, the ASAP project can help preadolescents develop a balanced and mindful approach to their social media usage, mitigating the potential negative effects of addiction and promoting their overall well-being.

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1.7. Public, Private and Common Realm

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Introduction

The use of public space by young people — including adolescents and preadolescents — has been widely studied across disciplines. While these fields often cite one another, genuinely interdisciplinary research programmes remain rare. This text builds on that body of work while recognising the need for more integrated approaches.

The public/private debate in relation to the use of social media revolves around the boundaries and visibility of personal information and interactions within the online space. Social media platforms provide users with the opportunity to share content, engage in conversations, and connect with others. However, this engagement often blurs the distinction between public and private spheres. When preadolescents engage with social media platforms, they navigate a complex terrain, where also literature is continually evolving. The state of the literature on this topic of public/private is dynamic as new platforms emerge, privacy concerns evolve, and user practices adapt.

Researchers have made significant contributions to understanding the complex interplay between privacy, visibility, and social media use (see Boyd, 2008, 2014). However, there are still ongoing debates and gaps in knowledge, particularly regarding the implications of platform algorithms, the role of user agency in privacy management, the impact of social media use on specific communities and groups (marginalised communities, preadolescents, adolescents) and the ways in which privacy concerns intersect with issues of power and inequality also in digital spaces.

By considering the perspectives of urban planning, psychology, anthropology, and other relevant fields, this research aims to provide a holistic understanding of young people's utilisation of public space. This understanding can then be applied to the analysis of preadolescents' engagement with social media, considering factors such as privacy management, self-presentation, identity formation, and social relationships. An understanding can be developed regarding how preadolescents utilise public spaces and navigate the public/private dynamics within the digital realm of social media.

Urban public and private space

The most extensive line of studies is probably the one that focuses on the use of public spaces in an urban environment. Starting in the 1970s, an international research program sponsored by UNESCO (e.g. Lynch, 1977) began the investigation of social (and sometimes antisocial) practices and behaviours in the urban contexts of many cities in the world. At the same time, some attempts to study young people' perception of these spaces and their use were developed. This piece of research also led to forms of participatory intervention, aimed at including adolescents and preadolescents as stakeholders in the design and redesign of some urban public spaces. Alongside this trend there were some studies that investigated the evolution of the phenomenon even outside the strictly urban context (Valentine, 1997; Matthews et al., 2000).

These pieces of research have helped to bring out the problem of the role of young people in contemporary society, fuelling the debate on the opportunity or need for their integration into

common public spaces as an alternative to both the strictly private one of the homes and the public but highly regulated one of the schools. On one hand the vision proposed the creation of additional spaces dedicated to youth activities (activities usually appropriately codified and regulated, therefore socially accepted), but on the other hand this vision was contested and considered a form of "tokenism", not different from the creation of small urban reserves, inevitably limited and inadequate for the participation of this group of citizens, with their needs and aspirations, in the life of the urban community as a whole (Matthews, 1995; Matthews et al., 1998). In this context, the role of young people and their presence in public spaces was also explored with a view to safety: while the occupation of public spaces by older age groups (adolescents and young adults) was often investigated in terms of its association with urban decay, petty crime and drugs, the age groups corresponding to childhood and preadolescence have been more frequently examined as subjects to be protected from the dangers present in public spaces (Karsten, 2005), for example with controlled interventions and "making safety" from the dangers represented by the phenomena mentioned above (Faulkner et al., 2015). However, there are cases of conflict in the use of urban public contexts also between this age group and the adult one (or the general population), e.g., regarding activities such as skating (Stratford, 2002). The research showed that young people often ended up being excluded from the public space, because of their vulnerability to the dangers of urban and social decay, as well as for the perceived incompatibility between the activities specific to their age and the intended uses of public space (Gray & Manning, 2022).

In the following years, particularly between the 1990s and 2000s, the attention of much research shifted to the question of the privatisation of public spaces and its consequences on the social life of citizens, including the younger ones, and on the very concept of sociality (Voyce, 2006). In many cities, both wealthy and less wealthy, new commercial spaces have begun to attract citizens for an assortment of activities that partly replaced those typically associated with a presence in public space. The socialisation of young people to use these spaces has raised concerns about their early transformation into consumers (Schor, 2014) not only in the private home environment (where this process had already been underway for decades, mainly through the TV), but also in that of public life and social activities. Another consequence of this process, and a sort of evolution of the theme that has already emerged previously regarding the management of the presence of young people in public space, is the imposition of new limits and restrictions on the activity of adolescent and preadolescent users of these spaces. Limits were no longer imposed by the public authority (and therefore attributable to more general social norms), but directly by the managers of the commercial public space (Graham, 2001), according to logic that intentionally or unintentionally ignored principles of fairness in access and participation otherwise the basis of public life.

Digital public and private space

With the development of the Internet and digital technologies, our horizon has widened to include new types of intangible spaces created by websites, chats, forums, apps and social networks, which in part transcend and surpass the distinction between public and private spaces physically.

A large field of studies on the online presence of young adolescents and tweens has focused on the spaces constituted by multiplayer gaming platforms (Plowman, 2016). In this context, the interaction is game-oriented, with its rules and objectives, and is in most cases anonymous and, therefore, without direct repercussions on the lives of the children outside of the time dedicated to that specific activity. However, studies have shown that, like contexts of real social interaction, virtual ones end up

influencing the thoughts, emotions and behaviours of young people in other areas as well (Willett, 2017), for example through the anticipation. Research on this phenomenon focuses on online activity in other home and school moments (Kahila et al., 2021), or the creation of stable and complex peer relationships (Boyd, 2014). Much research has also been devoted to the negative effects of the quantity and quality of time dedicated to online activities on the mental life of children, such an example is the case of the so-called Internet gaming disorder (APA, 2013), or Internet addiction (Widyanto & Griffiths, 2006). However, research in this area is mainly concentrated on older age groups, and less on those of childhood and preadolescence (see Hawi et al., 2019).

However, the area that has most tested the distinction between public and private space in the digital age is that of social networks. The presence of preteens and adolescents in this new type of digital space has been extensively studied during the development and evolution of the different social networks. In the first phase, social networks quickly became an extension of existing friendship and peer networks (Lenhart et al., 2011), maintaining the distinctions between the private sphere and the publications in those same networks. However, the technically complex and non-transparent nature of online platforms soon made the management of user privacy problematic (Chen & Kim, 2014), especially the younger generations, also leading to a series of studies on the ability to understand and manage the boundaries between contexts, and the risks associated with an insufficiently informed use of these means. Subsequently, the use of social networks by young and very young people has expanded, with increasingly frequent participation in online communities (and therefore, shared digital spaces) alternatives to the real ones. These new contexts, such as those that have arisen on platforms like Instagram, Twitch and TikTok, have been the subject of further research in recent years, and are partly related to the issue of understanding and negotiating online public presence, as well as to the consequences of online activity on psychic sphere of kids (Faelens et al., 2021). Some studies have instead investigated the emergence of new phenomena within online relationships that challenge the very distinction between the public sphere and the online private sphere, as in the case of parasocial relationships with influencers and content creators (Kim et al., 2015). Preadolescents and adolescents have been found to develop familiarity and emotional attachment to these figures through the consumption of their content online and participation in online communities, despite never being in direct contact with them.

A recurring theme of research on the presence of children online is that of digital literacy (Meyers et al., 2013). The acquisition of technical skills on digital media is essential for understanding the limits of platforms and the potential risks of their use by adolescents and preadolescents. These skills can be learned in parallel with the social ones, in an integrated perspective of digital socialisation (Boyd, 2008).

Conclusion

This chapter examines the literature studying the utilisation of public and private spaces, both in physical and digital contexts. It emphasises the need to understand how young people navigate and experience these spaces, including urban public spaces and online platforms. When preadolescents engage with social media platforms, they navigate a complex terrain where the boundaries between public and private can become blurred. On one hand, social media platforms offer opportunities for self-expression, sharing personal experiences, and connecting with others. Users can create profiles, post updates, and engage in conversations with friends or even strangers. These activities often take place in digital public spaces where content can be accessed by a wide audience. However, privacy

settings and controls allow users to determine the level of visibility and restrict access to their content, creating a semblance of digital private spaces. The challenge arises when preadolescents navigate these platforms without fully understanding the implications of their actions. They may not have a clear understanding of privacy settings, or the potential risks associated with sharing personal information. As a result, their online activities can inadvertently expose them to privacy breaches, cyberbullying, or exploitation.

The public/private debate highlights the need to educate preadolescents about the complexities of managing their digital presence and the potential consequences of oversharing or engaging with inappropriate content. It emphasises the importance of promoting digital literacy skills, empowering preadolescents to make informed decisions about their online interactions and safeguarding their privacy. By considering the public/private debate when addressing the challenges within social media usage, the ASAP project can develop interventions and strategies that foster responsible digital engagement among preadolescents. It can promote discussions about privacy settings, guide preadolescents on managing their digital footprints, and empower them to create a healthy balance between public sharing and protecting their personal privacy.

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1.8. Cyberbullying

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Introduction

Although it has to be emphasized that there is no unique definition of cyberbullying, cyberbullying can be defined as “wilful and repeated harm inflicted through the use of computers, cell phones, and other electronic devices” (Hinduja & Patchin, 2014, p. 151) or to put it more simply “when someone repeatedly makes fun of another person online or repeatedly picks on another person through e-mail or text message or when someone posts something online about another person that they don’t like”. However, Pew Research Center (Vogels, 2022) defines cyberbullying as “offensive name-calling; spreading of false rumours about them; receiving explicit images they didn’t ask for; physical threats; constantly being asked where they are, what they’re doing, or who they’re with by someone other than a parent; having explicit images of them shared without their consent”; EU Kids Online Network (Smahel et al., 2020, p. 52) as “teasing someone in a way this person does not like; hitting, kicking or pushing someone around leaving someone out of things” via “face-to-face (in person), by mobile phone (texts, calls, video clips), on the internet (e-mail, instant messaging, social networking, chatrooms)”; Merriem Webster Dictionary (n.d.) as “the electronic posting of mean-spirited messages about a person often done anonymously”; UNICEF (n.d.) as “bullying with the use of digital technologies. It can occur on social media, messaging platforms, gaming platforms, and mobile phones. It is repeated behaviour, aimed at scaring, angering or shaming those who are targeted.”

Research showed that cyberbullying is most likely to occur concurrently with other forms of bullying, and children who are abused online are often abused offline as well (Waasdorp & Bradshaw, 2015). Nevertheless, there are several key differences between the two forms of violence. Namely, one of the main characteristics of cyberbullying, although not always, is anonymity (Toshack & Colmar, 2012; Heirman & Walrave, 2008). Compared to physical violence, people can be abused online 24 hours a day, seven days a week (Kernaghan & Elwood, 2013; according to Ciboci, 2018), and there is no safety in one's own home because a person can be abused anywhere they have access to the Internet (Tokunaga, 2010). Of course, this refers to all those cases in which children are protected in the safety of their own homes and do not suffer domestic violence. A big problem with cyberbullying is the unlimited audience (Kernaghan, Elwood, 2013, according to Ciboci, 2018), persistency, escalation (that may drive to suicide, for example), and the trace of the written word, due to which “the victim can re-read what the abuser wrote about her each time (...) the written word seems more concrete and realistic than the spoken one” (Pregrad et al. 2010, p. 8 according to Ciboci, 2018). Perpetrators of cyberbullying are often unaware of the consequences of this form of violence (Accordino, Accordino, 2011). Furthermore, “hurtful and harmful material published online can be easily copied, stored and shared through many channels (such as a social networking site), opening up the possibility for further harm due to repeated exposure of the material” (Smahel et al. 2020, p. 52).

There are different forms of cyberbullying (Wanjohi, 2018):

“Willard (2006) classified cyberbullying behaviours into seven categories: flaming, online harassment, cyberstalking, denigration, impersonation, outing, and exclusion. Flaming involves sending rude messages about a person to an online group or to that

person via e-mail or text message (Holt, 2010). Kowalski et al. (2008) indicate that flaming mostly occurs in chat rooms or discussion groups rather than private e-mail exchanges. Online harassment is where bullies repeatedly send offensive messages via electronic means to another individual (Willard, 2006). Harassment normally occurs through e-mail and public forums, such as chat rooms and discussion groups. Cyberstalking includes threats of harm or behaviour that are excessively intimidating. Denigration involves sending harmful, untrue, or cruel statements about a person to other people or posting altered photos of someone. (...) impersonation, which Bocij (2004) labels as 'masquerade', is where bullies pretend to be someone else and send or post material that makes another person look bad. The sixth category is 'outing', and it involves sending or posting material about a person that contains sensitive, private, or embarrassing information, including forwarding private messages or images. The final category is 'exclusion', where perpetrators cruelly exclude someone from an online group (Kowalski et al., 2008). A new category termed 'Happy Slapping' has emerged whereby adolescents walk up and slap someone while another one captures the violence on the camera phone, then the video is uploaded online (Kowalski et al. 2008)."

Patchin and Hinduja (2020, p. 31), as a form of cyberbullying, also point out sextortion, which can be defined "as the threatened dissemination of explicit, intimate, or embarrassing images of a sexual nature without consent, usually for the purpose of procuring additional images, sexual acts, money, or something else".

The prevalence of cyberbullying

There are numerous studies on this topic. For example, research by the Pew Research Center (Vogels, 2022) shows that nearly half of US teens ages 13 to 17 (46%) have experienced cyberbullying, with offensive name-calling being the most reported. In addition to the above, among the frequent forms of cyberbullying, teens mentioned spreading false rumours about them and receiving explicit images they didn't ask for. At the same time, compared to boys, girls are more often exposed to all the mentioned forms of violence.

One of the frequent forms of cyberbullying includes sextortion which can be defined as "the threatened dissemination of explicit, intimate, or embarrassing images of a sexual nature without consent, usually for the purpose of procuring additional images, sexual acts, money, or something else" (Patchin, Hinduja, 2020, p. 30). Research conducted in the US among children 12 to 17, for example, shows that "approximately 5% of students reported that they had been the victim of sextortion, while about 3% admitted to threatening others who had shared an image with them in confidence" (Patchin, Hinduja, 2020, p. 30).

When it comes to preadolescents, Patchin and Hinduja (2022) conducted a survey among 1034 children ages 9 to 12 and concluded that "one in five 9- to 12-year-olds has been exposed to cyberbullying as a witness, a target, or an aggressor (...), boys were significantly more likely to have cyberbullied others, but there was no difference with respect to victimization" (Patchin & Hinduja, 2022, p. 422). In their research, 14,5% of preadolescents (children between the ages of 9 and 12) have been cyberbullying victims (Patchin & Hinduja, 2022, p. 418). Furthermore, "more than two-thirds of tweens who had been cyberbullied said it negatively impacted their feelings about themselves while

13.1% said it affected their physical health. Three out of four girls (74.7%) shared that victimization affected their feelings about themselves.” (Patchin & Hinduja, 2022, p. 423). Younger students at 9 are more likely than older students to assist (step in to defend, support, or otherwise assist) when they see cyberbullying.

Figure 1: Cyberbullying exposure among US teens (Source: Vogels, 2022)

Although many studies can be mentioned on this topic, with the mentioned American research, below are the key results related to exposure to cyberbullying obtained as part of the global EU Kids Online representative survey in which 19 European countries⁷ participated. Smahel et al. (2020), based on participants in all countries, a total of 25,101 children aged 9 to 16, draw the following key conclusions:

- In all countries, more children report being a victim than an aggressor.
- In most countries, more than 20% of children experience victimization. If we are talking only about children aged 9 to 11, 20% experienced victimization, with significant differences observed in the countries. For example, while 5% and fewer such cases were recorded in Croatia, Slovakia, Estonia, and Poland, every third child had such an experience (Smahel et al., 2020).

⁷ Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, Flanders – Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Malta, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russian Federation, Republic of Serbia, The Slovak Republic, Spain, and Switzerland.

- While in most countries, in 10% and fewer cases, children aged 9 to 11 admitted that they were treated by someone else in a hurtful or nasty way, in Poland 27% of children admitted it.
- Most countries have no substantial gender difference in victimization or aggression. In Switzerland, France, and Malta, slightly more girls are victimized than boys. More boys are aggressors in the Czech Republic, Spain, Poland, and Romania.

All the mentioned research shows that children encounter various forms of cyberbullying in their earliest days, practically as soon as they start using smartphones and accessing the Internet independently. This means that all preventive activities should be implemented as early as possible to protect children from various inappropriate forms of online behaviour.

Conclusion

Cyberbullying is a complex and evolving form of violence that affects children from a very young age, particularly as their access to smartphones and online platforms increases. While definitions vary slightly across institutions, common elements include repeated, harmful behaviour carried out through digital means, often marked by anonymity, persistence, and a potentially unlimited audience. The psychological toll on victims—ranging from self-esteem issues to anxiety and depression—is significant, and research shows that girls are particularly vulnerable to certain forms of cyberbullying, such as sextortion and exposure to explicit content.

Findings from international studies, including those from the U.S. and the EU Kids Online survey, indicate that a significant portion of preadolescents have already experienced or witnessed cyberbullying, with some even participating in it. Despite some regional differences, the overall trend is clear: cyberbullying is prevalent and starts early. This highlights the urgent need for early, comprehensive prevention and education programs—targeted not just at children, but also at parents, educators, and other stakeholders—to foster empathy, digital literacy, and a deeper understanding of the consequences of online behaviour.

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1.9. Cyberbullying Prevention in the Classroom

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Origins of bullying

The instinctual drive to survive is a common trait among all living beings, stemming from the competition that arises due to the limited natural resources and multitude of species on our planet. Throughout history, the pursuit of outperforming others and overcoming obstacles has remained ingrained in human nature as our race has evolved. This survival instinct, along with a competitive environment, extends into various aspects of life, including education, social interactions, and the economy. However, the prevalence of this competitive hierarchy varies across cultures, influenced by ethical systems, traditions, and the level of government control.

From an early age, children are taught to strive for excellence as they enter grade school. However, this seemingly innocent lesson can transform as they progress through their education. In highly competitive educational and social environments, students often learn corrupt means to get ahead. These tactics may involve pressuring others for answers on assignments to achieve higher grades, which can lead to better college opportunities, or spreading rumours about fellow students. Such bullying tactics are concerning because when students realize their effectiveness, they may adopt them as a way of life. Engaging in habitual bullying can have a negative impact on countless individuals and contribute to corruption in the workplace.

Technological advancements are often associated with the progress of human societies. Innovations like the Internet have revolutionized the way people interact. While these developments have brought significant advancements in various fields, they have also facilitated the proliferation of transgressions. This is evident in the evolution of traditional bullying into the widespread issue of cyberbullying. While both forms share similarities in terms of tactics and methods, cyberbullying offers distinct differences. Unlike traditional bullying, cyberbullying allows perpetrators to hide their identity behind a computer screen, making it easier to harm victims without witnessing their physical responses. The distancing effect of technology often leads today's youth to engage in more cruel behaviour compared to traditional face-to-face bullying situations.

So, what exactly is cyberbullying? According to Wilkey (2023) it refers to the use of digital media such as websites, apps, and text messages to intentionally intimidate, upset, or harm someone. Cyberbullying involves repeatedly sending, posting, or sharing negative, harmful, or mean content about another person. In instances of cyberbullying, there are often bystanders, allies, or upstanders. Bystanders observe the conflict or unacceptable behaviour but do not intervene. Allies, on the other hand, support the person being bullied by offering their friendship and checking in on them. Upstanders actively try to stop the bullying by confronting the perpetrator directly or reporting the incident to a trusted adult.

Cyberbullying differs from face-to-face bullying in several ways. It can be harder to escape as it can occur anywhere and at any time. Detecting cyberbullying is challenging since much of children's digital media use goes unmonitored by adults. Furthermore, cyberbullying can be highly public, with large numbers of online users witnessing and even joining in on the harassment. Although the target is often

exposed publicly, cyberbullies can conceal their identity by posting anonymously or using pseudonyms. Moreover, since cyberbullying lacks face-to-face interaction, the perpetrators may not fully comprehend the implications of their actions.

Understanding the influencing factors on teachers' coping with cyberbullying

Olenik-Shemesh et al. (2019) presents an in-depth examination of personal, teaching-background variables, and significant psychological variables that may affect teachers' coping with cyberbullying. The findings reveal that cyberbullying coping may be predicted by seniority of teaching, high levels of empathy, good communication with students, and teachers' self-efficacy, but not by age and not by gender. The interaction between teachers' self-efficacy and communication may also predict effective coping. It was also found that the association between teachers' communication with students and cyberbullying coping is mediated by empathy and teachers' self-efficacy. These findings have implications at both theoretical and practical levels. At the theoretical level, the research findings add considerable knowledge regarding teachers' coping with violence in general and with online violence in particular, by identifying personal factors that significantly affect the coping process. On a practical level, whereas other findings have pointed to a few main elements involved in the successful training of educational staff, including emphasizing the importance of encouraging the reporting of cases of cyberbullying, keeping teachers updated on new technologies and their use by students, and creating an atmosphere in which students feel safe to report cyberbullying (Englander & Muldowney, 2007; Li, 2008), the findings of the study indicate specific factors that should be implemented and emphasized in teachers' education training programs relating to coping with cyberbullying, an issue that has become central and challenging in schools (Aharonson, 2010). It is recommended that such programs include enhancing levels of teachers' empathy, their sense of self-efficacy, and their communication with students. Continued research on this topic is needed to explore various ways to develop effective communication and authentic discourse between teachers and students. On the other hand, the findings also indicated that there is no need to address age and gender when developing such an intervention program (Aharonson, 2010).

Other studies have found that when encouraging students to report cyberbullying, programs should meaningfully involve a parent or guardian (Snakenborg et al., 2011), raise awareness of educational staff to the phenomenon of cyberbullying and its implications, teach educators how to recognize and cope with cyberbullying, and increase supervision of students using technology for learning purposes (Patchin & Hinduja, 2010).

Researchers claim that despite some increase in awareness of cyberbullying, providing teachers with more specific programs for coping with cyberbullying is important to assist them with prevention and classroom intervention (Giménez-Gualdo & Carrión del Campo, 2018; Englander & Muldowney, 2007). Whereas most programs relate to identifying cyberbullying, its effects on students, and acquisition of tools for knowing how to manage cyberbullying incidents, many teachers report that their teacher training program did not properly prepare them for coping with it (Styron et al., 2016). Programs that will include components such as school and class atmosphere, social activities, cultivation of classroom relationships, and personal teacher-student relationships are necessary (Giménez-Gualdo & Carrión del Campo, 2018). The findings of the current study suggest specific variables that should be included in such programs. These variables relate to personal factors of the teachers that may increase their ability to cope with cyberbullying episodes and may fill the gaps in the existing programs. More specifically, the findings indicate training and education programs that include developing teachers'

empathy, improving communication with students, and raising self-efficacy may contribute significantly to teachers' coping.

Teacher-related personal factors seem to play a significant role in tackling cyberbullying incidents that have a negative impact on the school climate, according to the report by the US National Center for Education Statistics (NCES, 2011) on predicted crucial factors in teacher attrition, especially within the first year of teaching. Teachers report a high percentage of attrition because of working under a negative school climate and inappropriate student behaviour, such as cyberbullying (Styron et al., 2016). Thus, more specific, personal, targeted programs may prevent teacher burnout and attrition.

Finally, while planning teachers' education program for coping with cyberbullying, considering the educational parent-student-teacher triangle is vital. The development of sensitivity and empathy binds these partners and brings together their emotional, family, and personal experiences. Parent-teacher relationships may be conflictual and are one of the greatest challenges educators currently face, but such relationships are important in coping with violence and bullying (Oplatka, 2018).

Pedagogical approach to cyberbullying: some incentives for teachers

Over the past decade, digital services have unquestionably revolutionized the daily lives of all Europeans, offering new avenues for communication, information sharing, and the exchange of opinions and ideas. However, along with these advancements, digital services have also introduced new risks and challenges. The increased accessibility and anonymity provided by the internet have contributed to the pervasive nature of cyberbullying, making it more difficult to prevent and address. Cyberbullying can affect anyone, and its consequences can be devastating.

Globally, statistics (Fighting cyberbullying of young people across the EU, 2023) indicate that 1 in 3 children have reported experiencing online bullying. In Europe, the situation is no different. In 2020, approximately 33% of girls and 20% of boys in Europe reported encountering disturbing content online at least once a month. Unfortunately, the COVID-19 pandemic has not improved this situation. For over five years, cyberbullying has consistently ranked as the most significant issue for young people reaching out to the EU-funded Safer Internet Centers across Europe. By the end of 2022, nearly 1 in 6 contacts to their helplines were related to cyberbullying.

To provide a specific example (Fighting cyberbullying of young people across the EU, 2023), in Ireland, the Irish hotline reported in 2021 that 83% of victims of intimate-image abuse were female, with 73% falling between the ages of 25 and 34. Among the reported instances, half of the images were found on video sharing services, 23% were uploaded to image hosting services, and 19% were posted on social media platforms. These figures underscore the severity and prevalence of cyberbullying in Europe, highlighting the urgent need for measures to address this issue and promote a safer online environment.

Given the significant amount of time that children spend in schools, teachers often become the primary and most accessible adults who can offer support and guidance when it comes to issues like cyberbullying. As kids navigate the complexities of the digital world, they require trusted individuals who can intervene, provide resources, and create a safe environment. Teachers play a vital role in recognizing the signs of cyberbullying, fostering open dialogues, and educating students about online safety and responsible digital citizenship. By actively addressing cyberbullying in schools, teachers can empower students, raise awareness, and work alongside parents and administrators to create a

supportive network that promotes the well-being and mental health of young individuals. With their guidance and intervention, teachers can contribute significantly to combating cyberbullying and ensuring a positive and secure learning environment for all students.

Identifying signs of cyberbullying in students requires teachers to be attuned to their emotional well-being. Observing changes in behaviour such as depression, fearfulness, or distraction can provide insights into potential cyberbullying experiences. Additionally, being aware of social dynamics during lunchtime, in hallways, or other areas of the school can shed light on shifts in friend groups or conflicts among students. Listen for mentions of "drama" or "haters," as these terms may indicate cyberbullying situations. It's crucial for teachers not to hesitate in directly checking in with students to understand what they may be going through. Seeking support from parents, caregivers, the school counsellors, coaches, or other teachers can be instrumental in addressing the issue effectively.

When it comes to intervening in a cyberbullying situation, it's important for teachers to approach the matter seriously. It's worth considering that children are still developing crucial skills like empathy, self-control, self-regulation, and respectful online communication, depending on their ages. Such situations can serve as valuable learning opportunities for everyone involved.

The specific actions to be taken may be guided by school, district, or state policies, which might differentiate between incidents involving school-issued devices or occurring outside of school hours versus during the school day. It is essential to involve the students' families, school administrators, counsellors, and/or school resource officers, as appropriate, to ensure that interventions are effective and aligned with established policies. By working collaboratively and adhering to established guidelines, teachers can help address cyberbullying incidents and promote a safe and supportive learning environment.

Teachers play a vital role in preventing cyberbullying and promoting responsible digital media use among students. Beside parents (caregivers, families), teachers should be highly involved in educating students on how to navigate the online world in a respectful and safe manner. However, finding the right time and space for these lessons within the demands of the school day can be challenging. Thankfully, as technology becomes integrated into various aspects of our lives, schools and districts are increasingly allocating resources and time to prioritize these essential skills.

Here are some approaches to consider for cyberbullying prevention in the classroom:

- Foster a positive and safe classroom culture. Regardless of whether technology is used in the classroom, teachers can establish norms of respectful communication to guide students on what is considered acceptable behaviour. Creating a safe and caring environment is crucial. Providing resources, such as tips on how to respond to cyberbullying or contact information for helplines, can empower students to identify, respond to, and avoid cyberbullying incidents.
- Seize teachable moments for digital citizenship. When encountering situations related to cyberbullying or respectful online communication, teachers can step in and address them as valuable teaching opportunities. Encourage students to recognize "red flag moments" that evoke discomfort, worry, sadness, or anxiety while using digital media. Teach them the three recommended responses: supporting the target of bullying, taking action to stop cyberbullying, or reporting it to a trusted adult. Reinforcing anti-cyberbullying messages, even if they deviate from the planned lesson, plays a crucial role in prevention.

- Integrate cyberbullying lessons into the existing curriculum. Teachers can find connections between their current subjects and cyberbullying to address the issue directly. For example, exploring norms of online communication, analysing historical instances of propaganda and hate speech, or discussing bullying situations depicted in literature can offer opportunities to incorporate cyberbullying education with proper planning.
- Advocate for a comprehensive digital citizenship program. To ensure effective cyberbullying prevention, it is essential to involve the entire school community. Encouraging the adoption of a school- or district-wide digital citizenship program provides teachers with dedicated time and resources to address these topics directly. It also offers students consistent and frequent opportunities to develop their digital skills while supporting families in reinforcing positive online behaviour at home.

Conclusions

The issue of cyberbullying has become increasingly pervasive in today's digital age, posing significant challenges for educators and students alike. To effectively address this problem, it is crucial to develop comprehensive training programs for teachers that consider the complex dynamics of the educational parent-student-teacher triangle. This triangular relationship is vital in promoting a supportive and empathetic environment, where emotional, familial, and personal experiences converge.

Teachers play a critical role in preventing and addressing cyberbullying incidents. By fostering positive and constructive relationships with both students and parents, they can create a safe and nurturing classroom atmosphere. However, it is important to acknowledge that parent-teacher relationships can sometimes be conflictual, presenting one of the greatest challenges educators currently face. Despite these challenges, building strong partnerships between parents and teachers is crucial in effectively coping with violence and bullying, including cyberbullying.

In the development of training materials for teachers, it is essential to incorporate various components that promote a positive school and class atmosphere. This includes fostering a sense of community through social activities and creating opportunities for students to cultivate meaningful relationships with their peers. Additionally, cultivating strong teacher-student relationships is necessary for establishing trust, open communication, and a supportive learning environment.

Training programs should address the specific challenges associated with cyberbullying and equip teachers with the knowledge and skills needed to navigate this complex issue. By emphasizing the importance of empathy, teachers can develop a deeper understanding of their students' experiences and effectively support them in coping with cyberbullying. Furthermore, improving communication between teachers and students is crucial for identifying and addressing cyberbullying incidents promptly.

To ensure the effectiveness of training programs, it is important to consider the holistic nature of the educational ecosystem. By involving parents, educators, and students in the prevention and intervention strategies, a comprehensive approach can be adopted. This involves recognizing the emotional and familial dynamics at play and providing support to all stakeholders involved.

Addressing cyberbullying requires a multifaceted approach that encompasses the educational parent-student-teacher triangle. Training programs for teachers should prioritize the development of

sensitivity and empathy, foster positive school and class atmospheres, and emphasize the cultivation of strong teacher-student relationships. Educators can and should effectively cope with cyberbullying incidents and create a safe and supportive learning environment for all students.

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1.10. Implications of the transdisciplinary knowledge research for the ASAP project

Below, we have summarized the key implications of the conducted transdisciplinary research on the ASAP project and its main deliverables: the ASAP Educational Programme, the ASAP Educator Training Programme and the ASAP Key Recommendations for Stakeholders and Policymakers.

Implications for the ASAP Educational Programme

- The programme should be developmentally aligned with the cognitive and emotional capacities of preadolescents. Activities should be concrete, interactive, and relatable, helping students gradually develop abstract reasoning, empathy, and impulse control.
- The programme should scaffold digital literacy skills progressively, focusing on critical consumption of media, fact-checking, privacy awareness, and understanding algorithms. Learning should include hands-on practice and exploration of real digital content.
- The programme should address how online risks are shaped by peer pressure, family dynamics, and school culture. It should integrate learning scenarios that reflect common social contexts, like group chats, gaming platforms, and social media challenges.
- The programme modules should include discussions on how social media influences social identity, values, and group behaviour. These modules can foster critical thinking about norms, popularity metrics, and influencer culture.
- The programme should incorporate modules that raise awareness among preadolescents about how social media platforms are designed to exploit dopamine-driven reward mechanisms. These should promote mindful digital use, self-regulation techniques, and a critical understanding of persuasive technology (e.g. variable reward schedules).
- The programme should address how preadolescents interpret and navigate the blurred boundaries between public and private space on social media. Activities should explore online self-presentation, privacy, identity, and social connection in both real and digital public spaces.
- The programme should embed robust content on cyberbullying awareness, prevention, and response. This includes recognizing forms like flaming, denigration, impersonation, sextortion, and FOMO-related aggression. Emphasize empathy, bystander intervention, and safe reporting.
- The programme should include skill-building activities in emotional regulation, respectful communication, and digital citizenship. It should prepare students to be upstanders, not bystanders, and build a positive peer culture online.

Implications for the ASAP Educator Training Programme

- Educators should be trained to recognize age-specific challenges in self-regulation, identity exploration, and peer influence. They should use pedagogical methods that encourage reflection, perspective-taking, and emotional expression.

- Educators should be equipped to detect and respond to online risk patterns emerging in student peer groups. Training should include simulation exercises on common digital dilemmas involving friendship, trust, and belonging.
- Educators need to understand the neuroscience behind compulsive digital behaviour to effectively support students. Training should equip them with tools to teach emotional regulation, promote healthy online habits, and detect signs of addiction-like use.
- Educators should be trained to foster discussions about online privacy, digital footprints, and social norms. They should help students critically reflect on their digital presence and its real-world implications.
- Focus on enhancing educators' self-efficacy, empathy, and communication with students. Programmes should include role-play, case studies, and guidelines on working with families and mental health staff in cyberbullying cases.

Implications for the ASAP Key Recommendations for Stakeholders and Policymakers

- Educational policy should prioritize the integration of digital literacy from primary school onwards and fund structured, curriculum-aligned media education initiatives for all students.
- Stakeholders should support interdisciplinary approaches combining media education, sociology, and youth studies to better address the cultural dimensions of digital life in educational policies and campaigns.
- Policies should advocate for age-appropriate design standards for digital platforms and promote research-based digital literacy curricula addressing compulsive platform design and its psychological impacts on children.
- Policymakers must recognize the public nature of digital platforms and promote equitable access, safety, and literacy, particularly for younger users who are negotiating complex social and emotional challenges.
- National strategies should push for early cyberbullying prevention starting in primary education. Schools should be equipped with resources, reporting mechanisms, and clear anti-bullying protocols that address both online and offline behaviour.
- Support policies that embed comprehensive digital safety curricula in schools and prioritize funding for teacher professional development in online risk management. Encourage whole-school approaches including parent-teacher-student collaboration.

2. Desk Research Country Reports Summary

This chapter presents the executive summaries of the desk research reports conducted in all partner countries (in alphabetical order): Czech Republic, Croatia, Italy, Portugal, and Slovenia. Each country report offers a concise and comprehensive overview of the intersection between preadolescents, digital media, and the country-specific context, based on an in-depth analysis of existing data, documents, and previous research. The full desk research reports can be accessed on the ASAP project's website: <https://www.socialmediakids.eu>.

Below, the key findings from each partner country are summarised and organised under the following topics: statistical data, national research on social media and (pre)adolescents, good practice examples, and legislation and regulation.

2.1. Czech Republic

Statistical data (Digital, 2023; DESI, 2022)

- Czechia's total population was 10.49 million in January 2023.
- There were 9.61 million internet users in Czechia at the start of 2023, when internet penetration stood at 91.6%.
- Czechia was home to 8.07 million social media users in January 2023, equating to 76.9% of the total population.
- A total of 15.08 million cellular mobile connections were active in Czechia in early 2023, with this figure equivalent to 143.8% of the total population.

National research on social media and (pre)adolescents (Kopecký, 2019)

- The Czech Republic has seen an array of surveys and studies examining the relationship between social media and (pre)adolescents, particularly in areas of safety, risk prevention, and cyberbullying.
- These investigations have generated valuable insights into how (pre)adolescents interact with social media, focusing on online safety, risk prevention, and cyberbullying, highlighting challenges and opportunities in the digital landscape.
- Young Czechs aged 11 to 15 comprise 8% of social network "problem users," higher than previous data. Girls show more problematic behaviours with social networks, while boys excel in computer gaming.
- Czech children are divided into four categories of social media use intensity: non-users (22%), normal users (52%), intensive users (18%), and problematic users (8%).
 - Don't use social networks (22%) – they experience reduced support from their peers, are less physically active, but they also do not tend to use addictive substances and are successful in the school environment.
 - Use social networks daily, but in a reasonable amount (52%) – they have the best ratings of overall life satisfaction, they do not particularly excel in any of the other

monitored indicators, but at the same time, they do not show poor results or risks either.

- Intensive (at every spare moment) use of social networks (18%) – they have the best relationships with peers and are also the most physically active, on the other hand, they have a greater tendency to use addictive substances (compared to "normals" and non-users), increased risk of cyberbullying and bullying.
- Problematic use (8%) – the most problematic group characterized not only by an extremely high amount of time spent in front of screens but also by low life satisfaction, the risk of depression, bullying, and cyberbullying, disharmonious relationships in the family and among peers. This group also has the highest inclination to use addictive substances.
- A significant proportion (8%) of Czech schoolchildren exhibit a problematic social media use (PSMU), which encompasses a range of behaviours and outcomes that can negatively affect the well-being of young users, such as excessive time spent online, cyberbullying, privacy concerns, social isolation etc., with gender differences becoming more pronounced as age increases.
- Around 22.5% of children aged 11 to 15 prefer discussing personal matters online over face-to-face interaction, increasing with age.
- About 16% of children between 11 and 15 have daily contact with friends they met online, with intensive and problematic users more likely to have such contact.
- Over half (55%) of parents are unaware of their children's online activities, especially in the case of problematic users.
- The 'Czech Children in the Cyberworld' report reveals alarming trends: many children ignore age limits on social media, YouTube is increasingly popular, and TikTok's usage is surging among the youth.
- Prevention methodologists⁸ play a crucial role in Czech schools, addressing digital safety issues like cyberbullying, sexting, and risky online behaviour, and working to create a safe learning environment.
- Methodologists highlight increasing concerns about cyber security issues such as online addiction and cyberbullying, and their role in primary prevention efforts.
- Completion of specialized training for prevention methodologists is hindered by time constraints and inadequate compensation, with only 50 % having completed the necessary training.
- Methodologists spend an average of 80 to 100 minutes per week on their duties, focusing on primary prevention for pupils and administrative tasks.

⁸ In the Czech school system, prevention methodologists play a crucial role in ensuring the safety and well-being of students. These professionals are unique to the Czech Republic and may not exist in the same capacity in other countries. They are responsible for addressing various issues related to student welfare, including those arising from the use of digital technologies and social media. Prevention methodologists are typically appointed within schools and are specifically trained to identify and address risks and challenges faced by students.

- Research on children's homes indicates that children from these environments are more vulnerable to risky online situations compared to the general child population, often creating and sharing intimate material online.
- The results from children's homes research compared with the Czech Children in the Cyberworld study suggest that children from children's homes encounter more risky situations online.

Good practice examples

Effective approaches for addressing social media in schools and other contexts have been identified, serving as inspiration for the ASAP project:

- JSNS Educational Programme (in Czech: JSNS – Jeden svět na školách / in English: OWIS – One World in Schools). The JSNS initiative by People in Need, a Czech humanitarian organization, fosters critical thinking and encourages active civic engagement among students via multimedia teaching sessions. Since 2001, it has covered topics like human rights, media education, and environmental issues, using documentaries and online materials. Films are freely accessible on their website, offering students resources in Czech and English language.
- "DigiStories: Nela" is a video game that simulates social networking to facilitate classroom discussions on cyberbullying. Through its realistic portrayal, it enables students to grasp the nature and impacts of cyberbullying. Players navigate a fictional platform, resembling Instagram or YouTube, where characters like Nela and Anežka experience cyberbullying. DigiStories facilitates post-game discussions in class, suitable for ages 11-15, delving into behavioural shifts on social media and intergenerational communication differences. This educational tool was co-created by the JSNS program and Charles Games, noted for educational innovation.
- Caught in the Net (Documentary): The documentary explores online child sexual abuse, using adult actresses to demonstrate predators' tactics on fake social media accounts. "In the Net: Behind the School" is a version for viewers aged 12+, providing guidance and prevention measures for children. An associated website, <https://vsitifilm.cz/>, offers guidance for parents, teachers, children, and potential predators to prevent further abuse.
- Bullying Minimization Program: This program addresses bullying in elementary schools through workshops and consultations. Teachers learn to create a safe classroom climate, recognize bullying stages, handle conversations with involved parties, and cooperate with relevant organizations. Consultations help schools implement anti-bullying strategies, fostering teamwork among teachers and enhancing crisis response. Developed strategies enable effective bullying prevention and management within schools.

Legislation and regulation

In the Czech Republic, there is currently no dedicated legislation that provides protection to users specifically against abusive behaviour on the Internet.

School Prevention Methodologist:

- According to Decree No. 72/2005 Coll., schools in the Czech Republic must establish a school prevention methodologist position.

- Prevention methodologists work alongside educational counsellors, psychologists, and educators in counselling and prevention services for students.
- They create inclusive environments for students with behavioural disorders, ensuring smooth integration into the school community.
- Prevention methodologists focus on preventing socially pathological phenomena, including bullying, substance abuse, truancy, and risky behaviours.
- They collaborate with teachers, assess warning signs, provide counselling, and contribute to the school's Minimum Prevention Program.

Methodological Recommendation on Primary Prevention of Risky Behaviour:

- The School Prevention Program (SPP) is essential in addressing and managing risky behaviours within Czech schools.
- The SPP provides guidelines and procedures for handling risky behaviours effectively.
- The process involves steps such as identification, reporting, assessment, intervention, and monitoring/follow-up.
- Collaboration among teachers, prevention methodologists, school psychologists, parents, and experts are emphasized.

System for Recording Prevention Activities (SEPA):

- The SEPA system is an online platform in the Czech Republic used to record prevention activities in schools.
- It centralizes prevention efforts documentation, ensuring a systematic approach to addressing social issues and risks.
- SEPA supports the implementation of the Minimum Prevention Program to create a safe school environment.
- It helps schools document prevention activities, monitor progress, and cooperate with regional prevention methodologists.
- SEPA collects information on school-based primary prevention for data-driven development of effective strategies at various levels.

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2.2. Croatia

Statistical data

The Republic of Croatia has 3,871,833 inhabitants, of which 1,865,129 are men (48.17%), and 2,006,704 are women (51.83%) (Croatian Bureau of Statistics, 2022a). 86% of households in Croatia have access to the Internet. Data from the Croatian Bureau of Statistics (2022c) show that "individuals most often use the Internet to send messages (93%), to collect information about products and services (93%), to read daily news and magazines (87%), to use an e-mail (83%), watch videos (79%), telephony and video calls (77%) and to participate in social networks (73%)".

The share of the population between the ages of 0 and 14 is 14.27% (Croatian Bureau of Statistics, 2022a). According to the Population Census, it is estimated that in Croatia, there are 40,644 children aged eleven, 39,767 children aged twelve, and 39,589 children aged thirteen (Croatian Bureau of Statistics, 2022b, 3). Regarding social media, Croatian children between 9 and 11 spend 119 minutes daily, while children between 12 and 14 spend 162 minutes daily (Smahel et al., 2020, p. 23). Almost every third child between the ages of 9 and 11 and almost half of the children ages 12 and 14 use a smartphone several times daily or all the time to access the Internet (Smahel et al., 2020, p. 21). Furthermore, almost every third child between 9 and 11 (32%) visits social networking sites daily (Smahel et al., 2020).

National research on social media and (pre)adolescents

The usage of social networks increases with the child's age - 35.0% of children aged 9 to 11, 68.1% of children aged 12 to 14, and 76.8% of children aged 15 to 17 have their profile on a social network or online video game site they were using at the time of the study. As for the age of 12 to 14, YouTube is used by 52.4% of them, Facebook 50.6%, Instagram 44.9%, WhatsApp 26.8%, Snapchat 21.1%, Viber 19.8%, Google 18.7%, and Messenger 17.8% (Ciboci et al., 2020). 63.9% of children aged 12 to 14 accept a request only if they know that person, 37.8% of them only accept a request if they have mutual friends, 25.7% only accept a request if they know that person very well, 9.2% accept a request only if their parents/guardians approve it. In comparison, 6.8% usually accept all requests. In addition to communicating with unknown people on the Internet, research has shown that so far, 14% of children have met in person with a person they met on the Internet, while such activities increase with age (aged 15 to 17 - 26.8%; aged 12 to 14 - 12.0% and aged 9 to 11 - 3.0%).

Results show that 79% of Croatian children aged 12 to 14 feel safe online and have a positive attitude about communicating with people online or seeking online support or information. Negative experiences online, such as being exposed to online sexual content, aggressive content, and other types of unwanted content; inappropriate contacts; online harassment and bullying; hacking; sharing personal information; damage to reputation; and also viruses, spam, pop-ups, and online advertisements were reported by 10% of them, and 66% stated that they know how to react to online behaviours of others which they do not like (Smahel et al., 2020). Results also showed that 5% of them were exposed to victimization in the past year (on or offline), and 2% of them suffered aggression in the past year (on or offline) (Smahel et al., 2020). Older children (6.4% of children aged 12 to 14 and 11.8% of children aged 15 to 17) are more exposed to electronic violence than younger children (4% aged 9 to 11). The most frequent forms of violence include receiving hurtful or inappropriate messages

(61%), followed by being excluded or left out of a group or activity (33%), and publishing and transmitting hurtful messages where others can see them (Ciboci et al., 2020). Personal data misuse is experienced in 2% of Croatian children (9-11 years old), and 7% of them got a virus or spyware on a device (e.g., phone, tablet, computer) (Smahel et al., 2020).

Good practice examples

In Croatia, informal media education is highly developed. Civil society associations that have been working for many years on media and digital literacy of media users of all ages, including preadolescents, play a vital role in this. The Croatian country report provides an overview of some of the best examples of good practice in this area, such as the activities of the Association for Communication and Media Culture and the Safer Internet Centre, as well as educational materials available at the portal Medijskapismenost.hr.

Legislation and regulation

Croatia has no special law regulating social media use, misuse, and abuse. However, different aspects of the use of the Internet and social media to protect users are found in different laws, such as the Criminal Code (Official Gazette 125/11, 144/12, 56/15, 61/15, 101/17, 118/18, 126/19, 84/21), which provides severe penalties for child pornography and introducing children to pornography, criminal offenses against reputation and honour, disclosure of information from child's private life, hate speech. At the level of educational institutions, the Ordinance on the criteria for imposing pedagogical measures (Official Gazette 94/15, 03/17) on primary and secondary school students should be mentioned.

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2.3. Italy

Statistical Data

Official statistical sources do not provide data on users under 16, as social media platforms do not allow data collection or targeted advertising for this age group. The most comprehensive national overview comes from We Are Social – Digital 2023: Italy, which reports very high levels of internet and social media use among the general population but cannot directly describe the behaviours of preadolescents. For this reason, available information on Italian 11–13-year-olds relies primarily on academic and research studies.

Digennaro’s study (2022), conducted by the University of Cassino and Southern Lazio, directly examines the digital experiences of 11–13-year-olds. It confirms the near-universal use of social media among preadolescents (88%) and highlights the role of image editing, peer comparison and online validation in shaping body image and self-perception at a very early age.

The Digital Wellbeing – Schools (2018) Survey shows that most adolescents received their first personal smartphone during preadolescence (often at 10–12 years). Early ownership is associated with more pervasive use in later years and higher risk of problematic or addictive behaviours. Differences also emerge according to family education level: the higher the parents’ education, the later children receive a smartphone.

The EURES report (2021), although focused on older adolescents, provides important indicators for defining “problematic smartphone use,” showing that over 80% of young people display risk factors related to digital overuse, emotional regulation, compulsive checking and online dependency.

Together, these studies underline the strong link between smartphone access, social media use and wellbeing, and offer concepts and indicators useful for training and research activities.

National research on social media and (pre)adolescents

Three major initiatives offer relevant evidence for ASAP because they include preadolescents among their focus groups and propose educational pathways that can be adapted to schools:

- [Digital Wellbeing – Schools](#), which couples data collection with tested tools for teachers on digital skills and citizenship.
- [EU Kids Online](#), providing a European comparative overview of online practices, risks and skills among children aged 9–16.
- Duplicate bodies: social media use among under 14s (Digennaro & Iannaccone, 2023), which explores how preadolescents build identity online, the role of image manipulation, and the discrepancy between “real” and “edited” bodies.

These research projects combine empirical data with training interventions, offering models that can inspire the design of educational tools.

Good practice examples

The Italian context shows how legislation can actively shape schools' readiness to address digital citizenship and online safety. Two laws have been particularly influential in creating an institutional environment that welcomes projects such as ASAP:

- Law 71/2017 on bullying and cyberbullying requires every school to appoint a designated reference teacher, develop prevention strategies, and collaborate with families, law enforcement and external experts.
- Law 107/2015 identifies the development of students' digital skills, including the critical and aware use of social networks, as a national educational priority, thus encouraging schools to engage with innovative digital education proposals.

Schools are therefore expected to organise educational and cultural initiatives that help students become more aware and responsible digital citizens, while teachers are required to participate in continuous professional development. Although Law 107/2015 does not specify a fixed number of annual training hours, many schools define a minimum of around 25 hours per year, and teachers maintain autonomy in choosing accredited training opportunities.

To support schools, the Italian Ministry of Education provides training, tools, and a national database of "[Good Practices](#)", hosted on [Piattaforma ELISA](#), which collects examples of effective interventions against bullying and cyberbullying. The 2021 MIUR Guidelines offer criteria for designing, selecting and evaluating good practices, and call for the establishment of school-based Anti-bullying Teams and Emergency Teams. These structures reinforce the systemic approach promoted by national legislation and make Italian schools particularly receptive to structured, research-based initiatives.

Legislation and regulations

The Italian regulatory framework governing minors' use of digital technologies is shaped by both European and national legislation. At EU level, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) establishes that digital services cannot be offered directly to children under 16, unless Member States set a lower threshold (but not below 13). Italy has set the minimum age at 14 years, meaning that, in principle, no child under 14 can lawfully open a social media account without parental consent. However, this rule is widely disregarded due to the absence of effective age-verification mechanisms: platforms typically require users to declare their age but not prove it. As a result, both underage access and adults impersonating minors remain common, limiting the protective effect intended by privacy legislation.

Italian law also addresses minors' legal responsibility online. Children under 14 are never criminally liable; those aged 14–18 may be prosecuted only if professionals certify that they understand and can will their actions. Regardless of criminal liability, parents and guardians are civilly responsible for damages caused by their children. This framework, structured around the legal concepts of imputability (*culpa in educando*, *culpa in vigilando*, and *culpa in organizzando*) highlights the shared responsibility of families and educational institutions.

Italy was also the first European country to adopt a dedicated law on cyberbullying: Law 71/2017. While representing a significant step, the law is still under revision, requiring further regulatory interventions. The law focuses primarily on prevention, education and early intervention, requiring all schools to appoint a cyberbullying reference teacher, establish procedures for internal reporting and response, and involve families when cases arise.

To support implementation of Law 71/2017, in 2021 the Ministry of Education issued updated Guidelines calling for the creation of school-level Anti-bullying Teams and Emergency Teams, integrating educational, disciplinary and support functions. The 2021 Guidelines also refer to Law 107/2015, which introduced, among the priority educational objectives, the development of students' digital skills, also aimed at a critical and aware use of social networks and media, as set out in the [National Digital School Plan](#). Additional regulations relevant to digital literacy include Law 92/2019 on civic education, which explicitly incorporates digital citizenship and responsible online behaviour into the national curriculum.

In parallel with these legal measures, the national Safer Internet Centre [Generazioni Connesse](#) plays a key institutional role. Developed within the European “Better Internet for Kids” network, it provides schools with operational tools helping institutions translate legal obligations into concrete practices. Its guidelines, training modules and monitoring instruments complement national legislation and contribute to fostering safer digital environments for children.

Together, these measures create a comprehensive, though still evolving, regulatory and institutional environment that shapes the responsibilities and protections surrounding minors’ digital lives.

National initiatives

In Italy, the educational offer on social media is not limited to cyberbullying prevention. There are many training offers that address digital skills more broadly, following the DigComp framework, giving a different response and perspective to the need for the protection of kids.

Added to the programmes already mentioned, the report also highlights:

- [Patti Digitali](#), community-based agreements on shared digital rules for families and schools.
- [Patente di smartphone](#), a structured educational pathway treating smartphone access as a "rite of passage."
- [Parole O Stili](#), promoting respectful communication through a widely used Manifesto.
- [MEDIAEDU](#), the national network supporting media education.
- [Giovani Ambasciatori](#) (MOIGE), a peer-led programme against cyberbullying.
- Italian Data Protection Authority, which produces [privacy and data protection materials](#) for minors.
- [Open the Box](#), focusing on disinformation, social media and AI.

The report also presents initiatives developed by the ASAP partnership:

- [Fondazione Carolina](#), a national reference point for child online protection, with initiatives such as the [Rescue Team](#) (cyber emergency service), [TRACeD](#) (gender-based cyberviolence), [MinoriOnline.com](#) (information platform for parents), [Conessioni Delicate](#) (paediatric guidance on digital health) and [CyberJoy](#) (online wellbeing campaign).
- [Pepita](#), provider of “[lo clicco positivo](#)” and “[Solo per te](#)” educational programmes on digital environments, awareness, relationships and affectivity.
- [Le Nius](#), through the [Digital Bees](#) programme, supporting media and digital literacy through inquiry-based learning.

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2.4. Portugal

Statistical data

INE (National Statistics Institute) data show that:

- In 2019, around 80.9% of households in Portugal had Internet access at home and that the proportion of Internet users in the country was increasing - 76.2% of residents in Portugal aged 16-74 reported having used the Internet in the previous year (INE, 2019).
 - Younger people were signalled as those who most accessed the Internet and digital media, and mobile phone or smartphone were the preferred devices (INE, 2019).
 - A marked growth in mobile Internet access has been reported - 82.5% of Internet users use mobile media to access the Internet (INE, 2019).
- Data for 2020, deeply marked by the pandemic context, highlighted a 3-percentage point increase in the percentage of Internet users compared to 2019 (INE, 2020).
 - The population aged 16 to 74 years used the Internet and digital media with the main purpose of communicating and accessing information (INE, 2020).
 - Activities related to education were those that recorded the greatest increase.
 - The proportions of users who communicated with teachers or colleagues through educational portals (from 14.5% in 2019 to 30.8%) and who attended online courses (from 7.7% to 18.0%) doubled during 2020 (INE, 2020).
- 2022 showed the growing importance of Internet access in mobility and mobile means.
 - Households with children up to 15 years old continue to have higher rates of Internet access (99.2%) and broadband access (97.0%) than the generality of households in 2022 (INE, 2022).
 - Households with children are those whose access to the Internet has risen more (99.2% vs 85.7), both in terms of fixed Internet (95.6% vs 79.7%) and mobile Internet (63% vs 45.1%).
 - 81.8% of people aged 16 to 74 used a mobile phone or smartphone to access the Internet (INE, 2022).
 - The most frequent activities were exchanging instant messages (via WhatsApp, Messenger, etc.), 91.8%, and participating in social networks, 79% (INE, 2022). Activities associated with civic or political participation are those which continue to have a lower participation – only one fifth revealed having expressed their opinion on a topic on websites or social networks and 13.9% participated in consultations or voting (INE, 2022).

National research on social media and (pre)adolescents

In the Portuguese context, research specifically focused on media and digital practices of Portuguese preadolescents and their relationship with social media is still scarce.

- The smartphone is the most frequently used device. Preadolescents spend an average of 1.8 hours (9–10-year-olds) and 2.5 hours (11-12 years old) on the Internet daily. The preferred activities are listening to music, watching videos, communicating with family and friends, playing online games and visiting social networks.

- Instrumental and communication skills, such as saving photos or changing privacy settings or knowing what to share online, are the skills young people believe to master. They feel less confident regarding the mastery of creative and informational skills. Younger ages (9-12) are less confident users. The skills improve with age and gender matters as boys see themselves as more competent dominating the instrumental and creativity areas, while girls seem to perform best in the critical and social skills.
- Among young people between 12 and 17 years old, communication and technical skills stand out, but they still struggle to master creative and information skills. Boys report confidence in technical and information competences, and girls see themselves as more proficient in the communication and creative domains, and the space of social networks in the lives of young people is growing. Girls tend to use the Internet longer than boys (4 hours vs. 3.7 hours).
- The use of social networks starts between the ages of 10 and 12 (Rebelo et al., 2020). In her PhD study with children aged 10-12, Castro (2015) found the same trend, and in line with her results.
- Threats of most concern to the children are: identity theft, misuse of personal information, cyberbullying, pornography, and the possibility of someone hurting them (kidnapping, rapping) (Castro & Osório, 2015).
- Among young people aged 11-17 years, 19.5% had been victims of cyberbullying with gender differences. Males are more frequently victims of password theft, dissemination of unauthorised personal information (24.5%), defamation (when a person tries to hurt the reputation of someone, in this case using digital artefacts) (25.9%), publication of videos or photos without consent (25.2%) and exclusion from groups and online games (23.1%).
- Female individuals are more frequently the target of threats, insults, offences and extortion of intimate photographs. Aggressions most frequently promoted through the media are sexting (40%) and threats through messages/emails or offences through the net (34.2%) (De-Barros et al., 2018).
- In the 11- to 14-year-old age group, there is a higher appearance of aggression related to offending through electronic media (83.2%), distribution of intimate photos (67.3%), insults through e-mail or messages (62.4%) and threats through the same media (62.4%).
- Very often, victims of cyberbullying are also victims of bullying (75.2%), with 76.1% of the victims managing to identify the bully, although in the case of cyberbullying the crime can often be committed without the identity being revealed. The aggressors are most frequently school colleagues (53.7%), friends (45.4%), or classmates (42.6%) (De-Barros et al., 2018).
- 25% of children aged between 9 and 10 years questioned in the EUKO 2018 survey experienced disturbing situations online – bullying, confrontation with violent or sexual content, among others.
- Cyberbullying predominates over face-to-face bullying – more than a fifth of those who suffer or suffered from this type of aggressions indicated that it occurs several times a month, through mobile calls, text messages, dissemination through social media of unpleasant comments, and threats. 64% of victims of online bullying reported that the messages were unpleasant and hurtful. 1 in 6 young persons, victims of cyberbullying, admitted having done things against their will (16%) (Ponte & Batista, 2019).
- Sending and receiving sexual messages starts at a young age, from 11 years old. They also report exposure to user-generated content related to violent content and images against

people or animals, self-mutilation, hate messages, drug use, incitement to anorexia and ways to commit suicide.

- Girls are the ones who report feeling less safe and having more doubts about what to do when faced with unpleasant situations online.
- Online communication becomes an integral part of teens and preadolescents' lives, problematic use has been on the rise, including social media addiction (WHO, 2020). These situations of addiction tend to increase as age also increases.
- Contact with strangers tends to start early, from 10-11 years of age (Rebelo et al, 2020) and preadolescents tend to omit dangerous situations they experience in online contexts from their parents (Castro & Ponte, 2020).

Good practice examples

- Initiatives promoted by various sectors of activity have been identified in the Portuguese context. Some of them have been ongoing and arise from the establishment of partnerships and collaboration between the political, security and educational sectors.
- The good practices identified show a concern with the promotion of media and information literacy skills that not only allow young people to use the media and digital tools in a responsible and enlightened way but also provide adults with educational responsibilities with the fundamental skills to accompany and support them (young people) in dangerous situations.
- The initiatives identified in the Portuguese report also underline the importance given to the development of materials and tools that can be applied in various contexts and are useful for different audiences – schools, families and end users.
- Besides initiatives targeting specific groups (e.g. children, educators, other professional groups), Portugal has also been promoting initiatives that target the general population, namely: [Stop bullying](#); [Cyberbullying.PT](#); [No bully Portugal](#); [Mooc: Bullying e cyberbullying: prevenir e agir dá-lhe respostas! Saiba como reconhecer os sinais de alerta e como intervir!](#); [Bullying.PT](#).

Legislation and regulation

- There is no specific law in Portugal focused on cyberbullying.
- The research found several documents that contemplate criminal practices committed online, namely the Tutelary Educational Law (Law 166/1999 of 14 September) and the Student Statute and School Ethics (Law No. 51/2012 of 5 September).
- In general terms, Portugal is governed by international regulations, namely European Commission directives.
- One of the most relevant documents is the General Comment no. 25 on the Rights of Children in relation to the digital environment, which details the various ways in which the Convention on the Rights of the Child applies to the digital world, stressing the rights that must be considered – such as the rights to access information, freedom of expression, privacy and data protection, digital literacy, among others.

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2.5. Slovenia

Statistical data

- Slovenia's total population in January 2022 was 2.08 million with 112,286 preadolescents (aged 10 – 14 years), which account for almost 5.4% of the total population (SiSTAT, 2022).
- 1.87 million people were using the Internet (90% of the entire population) (DataReportal, 2022) and 93% of Slovenian households have access to the Internet connection (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2022).
- There were 1.61 million users of social media (not necessarily unique users; individuals using various social media platforms might have been counted several times) in 2022 (DataReportal, 2022). However, there is no information on the exact number of Slovenian (pre)adolescent users of social media.
- Although substantial progress has been achieved recently in terms of digitalization, the digital competences of Slovenes are still rather low – with only 20% of individuals expressing above basic digital skills (European Commission, 2022).

National research on social media and (pre)adolescents

During the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, an international study on "kids' digital lives in COVID-19 times" (KiDiCoTi) was implemented. The data for Slovenia revealed the following results (Safe.si, 2022):

- 54% of kids were more concerned about the increasing use of digital technologies (compared to the period before lockdown).
- 17% of kids reported skipping meals and irregular sleep patterns due to ICT overuse.
- 33% of kids reported actively trying to downsize the use of ICT and failing to do so.
- 60% of kids reported that they feel safe online; however, 30% reported that they were exposed to false news, and 14% reported that their exposure to unpleasant internet experiences had risen.
- 50% of kids have already experienced upsetting and bothering situations online and 32% of surveyed kids have been victims of cyberbullying (hurtful messages were either sent to them or passed around or they were excluded from a group or directly threatened on the Internet).
- 62% of kids have already been exposed to hate speech; however, they did not notice a rise in hate speech during the pandemic.
- 57% of kids have stumbled upon user-created harmful content (such as drug abuse, sexual content etc.) with 15% reporting the rise of such content interactions.
- 88% of kids (the highest percentage in the participating countries) have never been victims of personal information abuse.
- 25% of kids have had experiences with malware/viruses, but only 3% reported a rise in such experiences.

International Health Behaviour in School-aged Children (HBSC) study, which was carried out in 2018, revealed the following findings for Slovenia (NIJZ, 2019):

- There were 10.2% of (pre)adolescents playing internet games daily and showing signs of addiction, most of those being 13-year-olds.
- There were approximately 8.3% of (pre)adolescents displaying problematic use of social media.
- 40.4% of adolescents aged from 11 to 17 have daily online contact with close and distant friends.

Good practice examples

- **Safer Internet Centre Slovenia** has been established as the national project to promote and ensure a better internet for kids. It has three components: a) Awareness Centre Safe.si, b) Helpline Tom telefon, c) Hotline Spletno oko (Safe.si, 2022b).
- **Logout – Centre for Digital Wellbeing** provides free psychological help and support to girls and boys suffering from the mental health issues caused by social media, digital burnout, digital addiction and to victims of online abuse as well. Apart from (individual) counselling, the Logout experts also deliver various prevention-oriented lectures and workshops dedicated to kids as end-users, but also to parents and teachers (schools).
- **ARNES – The Academic and Research Network of Slovenia** is a public institute that provides network services to research, educational and cultural organizations. An important part of Arnes' role in the research and education community is user education and transfer of knowledge. Among others, Arnes conducts and delivers massive open online courses (MOOCs) on the safe use of modern ICT technologies, such as MOST-V for educators and MOST-VO for primary school students aged 9-14.
- **Saferkidsonline** is a web portal with excellent collection of educational materials for children and their parents related to online and digital safety. The site and all the materials are available in Slovenian language.
- **Project NEON** aims to promote non-violence among children, also tackling issues of digital violence and online safety. The project's activities are intended for (pre)adolescents, younger children and their parents, as well as for professional workers and educational institutions.

Legislation and regulation

- There is no law in Slovenia that would protect users against Internet abusive behaviour specifically.
- The rights of Internet users, together with privacy and security issues are regulated by the Electronic Communications Act, an EU-compliant law (Uradni list RS, 2022).
- The Slovenian Information Commissioner's Office offers help in securing personal data, but it also educates users on the formal steps they can take, should they find their rights have been violated (Informacijski pooblaščenec RS, 2022).
- Recently, the Guidelines on the use of screens in children and adolescents have been prepared by a consortium of experts. They are primarily intended for all professionals who work with children and young people in education, health care or other professional services (Medical Chamber of Slovenia, n.d.).

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2.6. Conclusions and implications

Key insights across five countries

1. Early and widespread access to digital devices

Children across all five countries are accessing smartphones and the Internet from a young age—often before age 10. Most preadolescents are active on social media despite age restrictions (e.g. Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, Snapchat). Time spent online is significant: from 1.5 to 3 hours daily, increasing with age and intensity of use.

2. High engagement, but not without risks

A clear segment of “problematic users” (e.g. 8–10%) exists in all countries. These users experience excessive screen time, sleep/eating disruption, poor mental health outcomes (depression, low life satisfaction). Online interaction increasingly replaces face-to-face communication.

3. Cyberbullying and online harassment are common

Between 25–50% of preadolescents across countries report exposure to: cyberbullying, exclusion, or threatening messages; hate speech, offensive user-generated content (e.g. pornographic, violent, or self-harm); data breaches or identity theft. Girls tend to be more exposed to emotional/relational aggression, while boys report more technical threats.

4. Low digital literacy and limited parental oversight

Despite being confident users, children lack critical, creative, and informational skills, making them vulnerable to manipulation, misinformation, or harm. Parents are often unaware or unequipped to mediate their children’s online activities, especially in high-risk groups. Children in vulnerable contexts (e.g. children's homes) show increased exposure to risky behaviour and lack adequate support systems.

5. Education systems are active but fragmented

All five countries show increasing school-level initiatives, including teacher training, prevention programs, and classroom activities. However, efforts are non-systematic, vary greatly between schools, and often depend on external partners (NGOs, EU-funded initiatives). National legislation often lacks specificity regarding children’s protection from online abuse and platforms’ accountability.

Implications for the ASAP project and its main results

The ASAP Educational Programme

- Start early: educational content should begin early (in primary education) to reach children before risky habits and patterns emerge.
- Focus on emotion and social wellbeing: teach children how to navigate peer pressure, body image issues, and emotional responses to online interactions.
- Strengthen digital literacy: go beyond technical skills—teach how to assess credibility, understand data privacy, and avoid manipulation or exploitation online.

- Include parents meaningfully: develop tools and sessions to help parents understand platforms, monitor digital behaviour, and support open communication.
- Gamified and interactive tools: use engaging formats (e.g. simulations, role-play, games like DigiStories: Nela) to address topics like cyberbullying or screen addiction.

The ASAP Educator Training Programme

- Train for risk identification: equip educators to spot signs of online distress, digital addiction, or social isolation in students.
- Empower school counsellors and teachers with specific roles/functions in the school, such as “prevention methodologists”: formalize and support their role, using tools like the Czech SEPA system as a model.
- Develop easy-to-implement resources: provide ready-to-use classroom materials, lesson plans, and scenarios that integrate into existing curricula.
- Address professional capacity gaps: include asynchronous options or microlearning formats to accommodate time-constrained educators.

The ASAP Key Recommendations for Stakeholders and Policymakers

- Policy-level advocacy: encourage legislation for minimum safety standards on social platforms used by minors; push for legal requirements for age verification and content moderation for underage users.
- Cross-sector collaboration: create national networks connecting schools, health professionals, child protection services, and NGOs; leverage existing programs (e.g. Fondazione Carolina, Logout Slovenia, Media Literacy portals) for national adoption and scaling.
- Support for vulnerable groups: develop tailored content and outreach strategies for children in care, children with disabilities, or socioeconomically disadvantaged backgrounds.

3. Desk Research Other Countries Report Summary

This chapter summarises the key findings and insights coming from the Desk Research Other Countries Report, which presents a contextual analysis of existing good practices and strategies for addressing the use and misuse of social media in schools, as well as educational initiatives aimed at preventing cyberbullying and enhancing digital and social media literacy among preadolescents in selected non-partner countries. The full Desk Research Other Countries Report is available on the ASAP project website: <https://www.socialmediakids.eu/>.

The selection of non-partner countries was based on several agreed-upon rationales following internal discussions among project partners:

- As ASAP is an EU-funded project, non-partner EU countries were prioritised (Finland, Belgium, Spain).
- Inclusion of non-EU countries from the Western world was considered important, given their potential for established and innovative practices (Australia, Rhode Island – USA, United Kingdom).
- Scandinavian countries, particularly Finland, were selected for their progressive and well-regarded education systems.
- Practical considerations such as language accessibility and the likelihood of retrieving relevant data also influenced the selection (e.g. Spain).

In this chapter, the summaries of selected country reports are presented in alphabetical order: Australia, Belgium, Finland, Rhode Island (USA), Spain, and the United Kingdom.

Each report follows a common structure to ensure consistency and comparability across the following topics: statistical data, national research on social media and (pre)adolescents, good practice examples, legislation and regulation.

3.1. Australia

Statistical data

Australia, with a population of over 26 million and 2.2 million children aged 5–12, has demonstrated an early and structured response to digital safety challenges. The Office of the eSafety Commissioner, established in 2015 under the Enhancing Online Safety Act, leads national efforts in online safety through schemes addressing cyberbullying, offensive content, and image-based abuse. According to the 2016–2017 Household Use of Information Technology survey by the Australian Bureau of Statistics, 86% of households had internet access, rising to 97% for households with children under 15. Smartphone use is nearly universal among children, and 14% of connected households reported a child aged 5–14 had encountered inappropriate material; 5% reported cyberbullying incidents.

A 2019 Headspace survey revealed that 53% of young Australians encountered cyberbullying, 44% experienced negative online incidents, and 21% reported harassment. Concerningly, 11% of teens shared images with strangers, and LGBTQIA+ children and those with disabilities face significantly

higher bullying risks. These figures emphasize the pressing need for both systemic prevention and support structures.

National research on (pre)adolescents

Multiple studies document the widespread exposure of preadolescents to bullying and online risks. The Australian Institute of Health and Welfare's 2020 report "Australia's Children" highlighted that 70% of children aged 12–13 had experienced bullying behaviours within a year, while 20% of children aged 9-10 reported weekly bullying. The eSafety Commissioner's Youth Digital Participation Survey found that 24% of children aged 8–12 had experienced unwanted online contact or content.

The Australian Child Wellbeing Project (ACWP) found that 75% of 8–14-year-olds used social media, with heavy usage linked to lower well-being. Children with disabilities and those from disadvantaged schools reported more bullying incidents. The "Growing Up Digital Australia" project further confirmed that children aged 8–12 spent around 12 hours weekly on social media and were more vulnerable to cyberbullying, particularly girls. Notably, many children lacked the skills to manage online risks, and parents and educators expressed a need for more support.

Good practice examples

Australia showcases a range of exemplary digital education practices led by the Office of the eSafety Commissioner, which provides programs for children (Young and eSafe), parents (eSafety Parents), teachers, and community groups. Programs focus on resilience, critical thinking, empathy, and safe online behaviours.

Digital citizenship programs, such as eSmart Schools, are implemented in many schools to teach responsible internet use. Social media policies are also adopted at school levels to regulate behaviour. The national curriculum includes digital literacy components under Digital Technologies and ICT Capability strands. Professional development opportunities for teachers are offered by institutions like the Australian Council for Educational Research (ACER). Parent-focused initiatives include education on screen time management and online safety conversations.

Legislation and regulation

Australia has a robust legislative framework to tackle online risks. The Privacy Act 1988 and Australian Privacy Principles regulate data protection. The Criminal Code Act 1995 and the Criminal Code Amendment Act 2019 criminalize online harassment and the distribution of violent content. The Enhancing Online Safety Act 2015 established the Office of the eSafety Commissioner, which has broad authority to enforce the removal of harmful content. The Australian Communications and Media Authority (ACMA) also oversees regulatory compliance and content standards in media and digital communications.

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3.2. Belgium

Statistical data

Belgium has a population of about 11.6 million (Statbel, 2023). Children under 15 represent roughly 17% of the population (Statbel, 2022), with a comparatively higher share in the Brussels-Capital Region, which is relevant given that education, media and youth policies are mainly organised at the level of the linguistic Communities. Belgium is highly connected: internet access exceeded 95% in early 2023, and around three quarters of residents were active social media users (DataReportal, 2023). As in many European countries, official statistics do not systematically capture social media use among children under 13; quantitative insights therefore rely largely on European comparative surveys such as EU Kids Online (Smahel et al., 2020).

National research on social media and (pre)adolescents

Evidence combines European comparative research and Community-based monitoring. EU Kids Online (ages 9-16; 2017-2019 data) documents early engagement with social media, video-sharing and online games, alongside exposure to online risks (Smahel et al., 2020). In the Flemish dataset reported in the EU Kids Online 2020 international report, 20% of 12-16-year-olds reported seeing hate messages at least monthly and 16% reported seeing gory/violent images at least monthly (Smahel et al., 2020). In the Flemish Community, Mediawijs coordinates Apestaartjaren and MediaNest monitoring. In a 2023 parental survey (Flanders/Brussels), 30% of 9-12-year-olds were reported to use social media with their own account and a further 18% via a parent-managed account (Mediawijs, 2023). In the French-speaking Community, the CSEM synthesises research and emerging issues (e.g., through the *Éclairages* series), emphasising early exposure, representation, online harassment and emotional impacts (CSEM, 2021). No comparable publicly available research specifically targeting preadolescents' social media use was identified for the German-speaking Community at the time of writing.

Good practice examples

Belgium does not operate a single national programme; good practices are largely Community-based. In the Flemish-speaking Community, Mediawijs supports schools through classroom resources and teacher support, including EDUbox toolkits (e.g., *Sociale media*, *Nepnieuws*, *Data en privacy*) and teacher-oriented resources (e.g., *Media Coach*, *No Cap*, *First Aid for Cyberbullying*). In the French-speaking Community, the CSEM coordinates recognised Media Education Resource Centres and provides practical guidance (e.g., *Éclairages: Les réseaux sociaux pour les enfants*) (CSEM, 2021). In the German-speaking Community, the Medienzentrum provides media resources and school-oriented activities. These structures are complemented by Betternet (Safer Internet Centre Belgium) and public service media (VRT/RTBF), which contribute to awareness-raising and educational resources.

Legislation and regulation

Belgium applies EU legislation relevant to children's online protection (GDPR, AVMSD, DSA). At federal level, general criminal provisions address behaviours such as harassment, threats, hate speech and cybercrime, including when occurring online. Schools have a general duty to ensure a safe learning environment, increasingly understood in guidance and practice as including protection from cyberbullying and online harassment. No single dedicated national law specifically addressing cyberbullying or minors' social media use was identified in the course of this review. Preventive and

educational measures are primarily addressed through Community competences; in the French-speaking Community, a key legal reference is the Decree of 5 June 2008 establishing the CSEM.

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3.3. Finland

Statistical data

Finland, with a population of approximately 5.5 million, includes around 314,000 preadolescents (ages 10-14), representing 5.6% of the population (Statistics Finland, 2023). As of 2022, internet penetration stood at 97%, and nearly all young people (16-24) used social networking services regularly. Among children aged 12-14, 97% had access to a smartphone, and 79% used it several times daily (Smahel et al., 2020). About 40% of Finnish children reported witnessing bullying or hate speech online. The most popular platforms for preadolescents include WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and Snapchat (Statista, 2021).

National research on (pre)adolescents

Surveys and studies indicate significant risks related to cyberbullying. A 2021 survey by mySafety revealed that nearly 50% of 10-17-year-olds had experienced online harassment, mostly on Facebook and WhatsApp (Helsinki Times, 2021). Another study (Hamal et al., 2019) using data from the Adolescent Health and Lifestyle Survey found that 12% of adolescents were cyber victims and 8.2% were cyberbullies. Girls and younger adolescents (ages 12-14) were more likely to experience or engage in cyberbullying. Poor perceived health and psychosomatic symptoms (e.g., headaches, tension) were linked to these experiences. Reports from the Protect Children organisation highlighted the alarming presence of CSAM (child sexual abuse material) online and the need for vigilance and robust reporting mechanisms.

Good practice examples

Finland has implemented a variety of initiatives to counter cyberbullying and promote digital well-being. The national digital literacy curriculum integrated into schools emphasizes responsible internet use, privacy, and critical thinking. However, the decentralized education system allows teachers to tailor implementation, leading to variability (International Literacy Association, 2015). The Yle Oppiminen platform offers multimedia resources for digital education. Parents benefit from resources like the "Parent's Guide to Social Media" and support from the Mannerheim League for Child Welfare. A flagship initiative is the KiVaKoulu® program, developed by the University of Turku and adopted by 90% of Finnish schools. This comprehensive anti-bullying program incorporates curriculum-based prevention, intervention through trained school teams, and regular monitoring. Evaluations have shown significant reductions in cyberbullying and improved student well-being (Salmivalli et al., 2013).

Legislation and regulation

Finland was the first country to guarantee broadband access as a legal right (Zeldin, 2010). Media education is a governmental responsibility, integrated into both education and cultural policy (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2013). Finland enforces strong privacy laws through the Constitution and the Act on Electronic Communication Services (917/2014), aligning with EU regulations. The Data Protection Ombudsman oversees compliance and provides guidance. Anti-cyberbullying laws are robust; schools are mandated to ensure safety and can enforce preventive measures such as smartphone restrictions during school hours. Unique to Finland, the 2015 Alcohol Act amendment limits alcohol advertising on social media to protect youth from harmful exposure.

While there is no standalone cybercrime law, relevant offenses are addressed within the Criminal Code.

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3.4. Rhode Island (USA)

Statistical data

Rhode Island, the smallest U.S. state by area, had a population of 1,097,379 in 2020, with children aged 5–14 accounting for approximately 117,000 individuals (Kids Count Data Center, n.d.). While the state's population increased by 4.3% over the decade, the percentage of children aged 5–19 declined from 19.3% in 2010 to 17.5% in 2020. Rhode Island consists of 24 school districts across five counties. Like many U.S. states, internet access is widespread, but specific state-level data on digital device ownership and internet use by preadolescents is limited. National-level data shows that only 17% of 8–12-year-olds use social media, while 47% play video games on mobile devices daily (Statista, 2021).

National research on (pre)adolescents

Research in Rhode Island indicates that most elementary and secondary students receive limited media literacy instruction. A comprehensive 2021 study by the Media Education Lab found that only 20% of students were exposed to key concepts such as the influence of advertising or media manipulation. Implementation of media literacy is often uneven, varying across districts and driven by educator interest and initiative. Cyberbullying remains a concern: 12% of middle schoolers reported being harassed online in 2013–2014, and 11.7% of middle and high school students reported cyberbullying in a 2018 survey (Skierkowski-Foster, 2021). However, no comprehensive longitudinal studies like EU Kids Online exist in Rhode Island. COVID-19 amplified existing digital inequalities between students and districts and highlighted challenges in digital pedagogy.

Good practice examples

Rhode Island benefits from the national and international expertise of the Media Education Lab, founded by Dr. Renee Hobbs. The Lab provides open-access digital literacy resources, curricula, and professional development opportunities, including its Summer Institute and the Mind Over Media propaganda analysis platform (co-funded by the European Commission). Other good practices include the Providence Children's Film Festival, which incorporates media literacy workshops and film-based educational programs, and media production activities through local libraries and after-school programs such as Media SMART! and the Make-a-Minute-Movie Challenge. These community-level initiatives demonstrate the state's innovative, if decentralized, approach to digital literacy and media education.

Legislation and regulation

Rhode Island passed legislation in 2017 recommending the integration of media literacy into the state's basic education regulations. However, as of 2021, this had not been implemented by the Department of Education (Media Education Lab, 2021). The 2021 Civic Literacy Act mandates civics education but does not include media literacy. Bullying and cyberbullying are addressed in six key legal and regulatory documents, including the Safe Schools Act and statewide school safety policies. Despite legislative efforts, systemic inclusion of media literacy in the school curriculum remains lacking, and progress relies heavily on local advocacy and voluntary adoption.

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3.5. Spain

Statistical data

Spain had a population of 47.6 million in 2022, with approximately 2.5 million children aged 10–14. The country is highly digitalized, with 85.6% of its population (40.7 million people) using social media. Each user engages with an average of six platforms, with YouTube being the most popular. While only 2.3% of users are aged 13–17, this demographic is heavily immersed in digital environments (Una vida online, n.d.).

Spain ranks 7th in the EU Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), with strong performance in digital skills, connectivity, and public digital services. Notably, 64% of the population has basic digital skills, above the EU average. Children and adolescents are heavy users of smartphones, tablets, and laptops, primarily for leisure and communication (Ballesteros & Picazo, 2019; Smahel et al., 2020).

National research on (pre)adolescents

Cyberbullying affects a significant portion of Spanish youth. According to Sestre et al. (2016), 10% of adolescents reported being bullied, and 7% experienced cyberbullying. The report also found that girls and younger children are more often victims.

Research shows that excessive screen time is associated with mental health concerns, such as anxiety and depression (Ballesteros & Picazo, 2019). Parental involvement appears crucial: teens whose parents set clear digital rules had more positive online experiences.

EU Kids Online (Smahel et al., 2020) highlighted that girls are more exposed to harmful online content than boys and report greater emotional distress. Spanish parents are more permissive with boys online and more restrictive with girls. This disparity may contribute to gender differences in online experience and safety.

Good practice examples

- PDA Bullying Platform: A national network promoting anti-cyberbullying strategies, certifications, and free-access resources for schools and families.
- Aprender a Mirar Foundation: Offers media education resources, case reporting tools, and training to protect young users.
- Cyberbullying Guide (Defensor del Menor, Madrid): A comprehensive educational resource with legal information, classroom materials, and parent-focused activities to tackle cyberbullying.
- Te pongo un reto: #RedesConCorazón: A 2019 project offering a best-practice guide based on the experiences of over 1,500 students and educators across Madrid.
- INCIBE (National Cybersecurity Institute): Leads public awareness campaigns, training, and the Cibercooperantes volunteer network. It also offers hotlines and support services for victims of online abuse.

Legislation and regulation

Spain has a robust legislative framework focused on child safety and digital rights:

- Law on the Comprehensive Protection of Children (2021) and Law 26/2015 strengthen protection against abuse and promote child participation in decisions affecting them.
- Organic Law 3/2018 guarantees digital rights and outlines children's right to education and online protection.
- National Cybersecurity Strategy 2019 and upcoming telecommunications and 5G laws reinforce digital security.
- Spain's Recovery and Resilience Plan allocates 28.2% of its budget to digital initiatives, reflecting its commitment to digital transformation and child safety online.

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3.6. United Kingdom

Statistical data

Recent studies demonstrate high levels of digital engagement among preadolescents and adolescents in the UK. Ofcom (2020) reported that 71% of 12–15-year-olds had social media accounts, a substantial rise from 45% in 2010. Popular platforms among this age group include Snapchat, Instagram, and TikTok, with average screen time reaching around 3 hours per day. By 2022, 97% of children aged 3–17 accessed the internet regularly, and even 87% of 3–4-year-olds went online. One-third of children aged 8–17 had created social media accounts using false birth dates, resulting in adult user profiles (Ofcom, 2023).

National research on (pre)adolescents

Multiple UK-based studies reveal significant implications of social media use on young people's mental health and well-being. NSPCC focus groups (2019) documented cases of cyberbullying, peer pressure, and body image issues among preadolescents. A 2022 study from the Universities of Birmingham and Manchester found links between excessive social media use and increased feelings of loneliness and depression. Additional research by Ofcom (2020–2023) and other organisations like the Royal Society for Public Health (2017) confirms that UK preadolescents frequently engage with Instagram, Snapchat, and TikTok. Children often lack full awareness of privacy issues, highlighting the need for robust digital literacy. Childnet International emphasised the role of parents in supporting safe online engagement, while the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO, 2021) underlined the importance of educating children about data protection.

Good practice examples

The UK hosts several high-impact initiatives addressing safe internet use and digital literacy. The UK Safer Internet Centre, a coalition including Childnet International and the Internet Watch Foundation, offers a comprehensive suite of tools, training, and events such as Safer Internet Day to raise awareness. The Digital Schools Awards program supports school-wide digital strategies and recognises excellence in digital education. The UK Council for Child Internet Safety (UKCCIS), a collaboration of over 200 organisations, promotes policy alignment and best practices in online safety. Childnet International's Digital Citizenship Program equips educators with classroom resources to foster responsible digital engagement. The #DITTO Magazine, produced by Alan Mackenzie Ltd., serves as an ongoing source of updates and practical tips for educators and families on emerging online safety challenges.

Legislation and regulation

The UK is actively reforming online safety policy. The Online Safety Bill, introduced in May 2021 and currently under committee review in the House of Lords (as of March 2023), proposes a regulatory framework requiring online service providers to prevent illegal or harmful content, including cyberbullying and content endangering minors. It outlines clear obligations for tech companies to implement content moderation and introduces fines and sanctions for non-compliance. The bill also proposes the creation of an independent online safety authority with the power to enforce transparency and accountability in digital platforms.

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3.7. Conclusions and implications

The conclusions and implications from the desk research in non-partner countries aim to provide additional or distinct insights compared to those identified in the five partner countries, as described in the previous chapter.

Key overall insights from non-partner countries

1. High policy and institutional investment in digital safety

Countries like Australia, the UK, and Finland have developed dedicated agencies, robust national strategies, and legal instruments to address online safety (e.g., Australia’s eSafety Commissioner, UK’s Online Safety Bill, Finland’s national digital curriculum). These efforts illustrate institutional readiness and structured policy responses, which contrast with the more fragmented or emerging approaches observed in several partner countries.

2. Emphasis on mental health and well-being

Research from Australia, Spain, and the UK establishes clear links between excessive social media use and mental health risks such as anxiety, loneliness, and depression—particularly among preadolescent girls. While such risks were mentioned in partner countries, they were more empirically documented and emphasized in these non-partner contexts.

3. Gender-specific risks and content exposure

Data from Belgium, Spain and Finland highlight that girls are more exposed to harmful content (e.g., self-harm, body image ideals, hate speech) and suffer greater emotional distress online. This nuanced gender analysis is less prominent in the reports from partner countries.

4. Decentralized media literacy implementation

In Rhode Island and Spain, despite legislative intent, media literacy remains inconsistently implemented—depending heavily on local educators or external organisations. This highlights a structural challenge: the gap between national policy and local practice, particularly evident in U.S. contexts. By contrast, the Belgian case illustrates a decentralised governance model in which media education is primarily developed at Community level, resulting in differentiated but complementary approaches rather than a uniform national framework.

5. Early exposure and misleading age use

Findings from the UK and Australia show that children join social media platforms earlier than allowed, often by misrepresenting their age. This creates scenarios where preadolescents navigate adult digital spaces without appropriate safeguards, a trend less emphasized in partner country reports.

Implications for the ASAP project and its main results

The ASAP Educational Programme

- Introduce emotionally intelligent digital literacy: the ASAP Educational Programme should include mental health and emotional resilience components, helping preadolescents recognize, regulate, and talk about their digital emotions (e.g., anxiety, fear, pressure).
- Tackle gender-specific risks and experiences: program materials should address gender-specific online risks—e.g., appearance-based pressures, online hate—and empower both boys and girls with context-sensitive coping strategies.
- Ensure age-appropriate awareness on privacy and identity: given the early and unsupervised entry into adult platforms, children should be guided on how to manage identity, consent, and personal data online from a young age.
- Create peer-support and help-seeking mechanisms: encourage peer-led digital safety discussions and integrate lessons on how and where to seek help when something online feels wrong—at school, home, or online.

The ASAP Educator Training Programme

- Train teachers in early detection of digital distress: equip educators with tools to identify emotional and behavioural red flags linked to online activity (e.g., social withdrawal, anxiety, or sleep disturbance).
- Build capacity for mental health-integrated digital literacy: provide training that connects digital skills with student well-being, using role-plays, discussion prompts, and check-in strategies during lessons.
- Support contextual implementation: offer adaptable program components that work across centralized and decentralized systems, supporting educators in tailoring content to school-specific needs, particularly where formal policies are lacking (as in Rhode Island or Spain).

The ASAP Key Recommendations for Stakeholders and Policymakers

- Align legislation with implementation capacity: encourage ministries and departments to bridge the policy-practice gap by ensuring that schools and educators are resourced and supported to implement digital safety curricula locally.
- Prioritize early and inclusive digital education: recommend that national policies begin formal digital citizenship education in primary education, accounting for increased early access and gender-specific vulnerabilities.
- Invest in central agencies or platforms: inspired by Australia’s eSafety Commissioner and the UK Safer Internet Centre, propose the establishment (or strengthening) of national coordinating bodies responsible for providing up-to-date resources, training, and child-friendly reporting systems.
- Mandate ongoing professional development: call for national education strategies to require continuous teacher training in digital literacy, online safeguarding, and student well-being—ensuring that teacher capacity matches the pace of digital innovation.

4. Conclusions

Key insights of the transdisciplinary knowledge research

Preadolescents represent a uniquely vulnerable population in the digital age due to their developmental, cognitive, emotional, and social characteristics. This stage of life, marked by intense neurological and psychological transformation, coincides with an early and growing exposure to social media, often before sufficient protective skills have been developed.

Cognitive and Psychosocial Development

Preadolescence (ages 11–13) is characterized by the rapid development of abstract thinking, metacognition, and executive functions. These capabilities, however, are still immature, resulting in limited impulse control and underdeveloped risk-assessment skills. Emotional sensitivity is heightened, with peer acceptance gaining central importance. Identity formation intensifies, often leading to increased susceptibility to peer influence, social comparison, and fear of exclusion.

Children in this stage are therefore more emotionally reactive and socially driven, making them particularly sensitive to online interactions, feedback, and potential rejection. This amplifies the potential harm caused by negative online experiences such as bullying, exclusion, or unrealistic social standards.

Digital and Media Literacy

Children's daily lives are increasingly embedded in digital environments. Social media platforms are now key spaces for socialization, self-expression, and exploration. However, while digital access is widespread, literacy often lags behind. Many preadolescents lack a comprehensive understanding of online risks, such as privacy breaches, algorithmic manipulation, or the emotional effects of overexposure to idealized content.

Media literacy remains unevenly taught and is often reliant on individual teachers or family efforts. Research suggests a need for structured approaches to help children critically evaluate media messages, understand the motives behind content (especially advertising), and navigate digital platforms with discernment and confidence.

Social Media Use and Psychological Impact

While social media can offer connection, learning opportunities, and self-expression, its use also carries clear psychological risks for preadolescents. Constant connectivity can interfere with sleep, concentration, and academic performance. The reward structures of platforms—based on likes, comments, and shares—activate dopamine responses that encourage compulsive use, especially in users still developing emotional regulation.

Younger users are also frequently exposed to marketing content shaped by influencer culture. These promotions often blur the line between entertainment and advertising, targeting insecurities around appearance, popularity, and success. The resulting fear of missing out (FOMO) and feelings of inadequacy can lead to anxiety and diminished self-esteem.

Public vs. Private Digital Spaces

Preadolescents often struggle to distinguish between public and private spaces in digital environments. Many engage in sharing personal thoughts, photos, or experiences online without fully understanding privacy settings or long-term visibility. This can expose them to risks such as unwanted contact, exploitation, or social backlash.

The blurred boundaries between public and private behaviour online complicate children's ability to manage their digital identities. Without guidance, they may overexpose themselves or misinterpret others' online behaviour, leading to misunderstandings or vulnerability.

Cyberbullying and Online Harm

Cyberbullying is a prominent and escalating issue. It includes a wide range of behaviours—flaming, exclusion, impersonation, sextortion, and sharing of private content without consent—and often occurs alongside traditional bullying. The digital nature of cyberbullying means that it can happen at any time, reach a broad audience instantly, and leave a lasting digital footprint.

Research shows that children experience cyberbullying at increasingly young ages, sometimes as soon as they begin using smartphones independently. Girls are particularly vulnerable to specific types of harassment, such as image-based abuse. Victims often suffer from reduced self-esteem, psychosomatic symptoms, and increased risk of anxiety and depression.

Studies confirm that many children have witnessed, experienced, or even engaged in cyberbullying, often without fully understanding its consequences. At the same time, educational environments are not always equipped to address it adequately, and teachers often feel unsupported in their prevention or response efforts.

Educational Ecosystem and Family Dynamics

The relationships between students, teachers, and parents are critical in shaping responses to digital challenges. However, these relationships can be strained, especially when schools and families have differing levels of digital knowledge or priorities. Teachers play a central role in mediating safe online behaviour, yet their capacity is often limited by institutional constraints or lack of training.

Effective strategies for addressing digital risks rely on coordinated efforts within the broader educational and family ecosystems. Promoting positive class climates, trust-based teacher-student relationships, and collaborative family engagement are all shown to be essential elements in building digital resilience among youth.

Key insights of desk research conducted in partner and non-partner countries

Across both partner and non-partner countries, a consistent picture emerges of preadolescents as active, early, and highly engaged digital users. Children typically begin accessing smartphones and the Internet well before the age of 10. Social media platforms—often not designed for their age group—are commonly used through age misrepresentation. This early exposure introduces both opportunities and risks, especially in the absence of adequate guidance or systemic protection.

Digital access is high, but literacy remains low

While children appear confident using digital platforms, critical digital literacy skills—including the ability to evaluate, verify, and creatively engage with content—are often underdeveloped. This gap makes them particularly susceptible to manipulation, disinformation, and exposure to harmful content. Schools are making efforts to bridge this gap through programs and teacher training, but the initiatives are often fragmented, vary by school or region, and depend on external actors rather than national systems.

Cyberbullying and emotional risks are widespread

Between a quarter and half of preadolescents across countries have encountered cyberbullying, exclusion, or offensive content online. Emotional and relational aggression is particularly common among girls, while boys are more likely to encounter technical threats. Studies from non-partner countries, particularly Australia, the UK, and Spain, link these experiences with increased rates of anxiety, low self-esteem, and depressive symptoms, emphasizing the urgent need for support mechanisms that also address mental health and emotional resilience.

Parental mediation is weak or inconsistent

Parents across countries, especially in more vulnerable or socio-economically disadvantaged contexts, often lack the knowledge or tools to support their children's online navigation. Some rely on restrictive approaches, while others provide little oversight. In either case, many preadolescents end up navigating online spaces alone—often adult-oriented spaces—with little protection or supervision.

Institutional responses vary in structure and effectiveness

Non-partner countries such as Australia, Finland, and the UK exhibit stronger, centralized policy responses with dedicated agencies, national strategies, and enforceable regulations. In contrast, partner countries show emerging but more fragmented institutional efforts, often relying on schools and NGOs to fill systemic gaps. Across both sets of countries, however, legislation related to platform accountability and children's digital rights is still evolving and often lacks clear mechanisms for enforcement.

Gender-specific risks and experiences are emerging

A nuanced gender lens reveals that girls are particularly affected by content related to body image, self-harm, and emotional abuse, while boys tend to engage in or experience more direct, externalized forms of online risk. These differentiated experiences call for gender-responsive education and intervention strategies—still underdeveloped in many partner country frameworks.

Media literacy is inconsistently implemented despite formal support

Even in countries where media literacy is formally recognized within curricula (e.g., Rhode Island, Spain, Finland), implementation depends heavily on local school commitment, educator motivation, and the availability of resources. This decentralization means that many children receive uneven or insufficient education on digital safety and responsible media use.

Conclusion

Preadolescents across all countries are navigating a digital environment that is rich in opportunities but fraught with unmitigated risks. Their early adoption of social media, coupled with low digital resilience and limited adult mediation, leaves them vulnerable to harm. While non-partner countries

demonstrate more structured policy and regulatory frameworks, both groups of countries face implementation challenges, especially at the school and family level. Addressing these systemic gaps through coordinated, inclusive, and age-appropriate interventions is essential for ensuring children's safe and empowered digital engagement.

Key implications for the ASAP project and its main results

Based on transdisciplinary knowledge research and desk research conducted in partner and non-partner countries, we have identified and extracted the following implications for the main ASAP project deliverables: the ASAP Educational Programme, the ASAP Educator Training Programme and the ASAP Key Recommendations for Stakeholders and Policymakers.

Implications for the ASAP Educational Programme

- Start early and age-appropriately: digital education should begin in primary education, anticipating early and unsupervised engagement with social media. Activities should match preadolescents' cognitive and emotional development levels, using concrete, relatable, and engaging formats (e.g. games, role-play, peer discussions).
- Emphasize critical and emotional digital literacy: teach not only how to use technology but how to think critically, reflect emotionally, and act ethically online. This includes fact-checking, understanding algorithms and persuasive tech, managing digital footprints, and building resilience to manipulation or exploitation.
- Address mental health and emotional wellbeing: incorporate modules on how digital experiences influence self-esteem, anxiety, fear of missing out (FOMO), and identity. Help children identify emotional red flags and provide coping strategies, especially around peer pressure, popularity metrics, and cyberbullying.
- Explore public vs. private digital spaces: raise awareness of privacy risks, online self-presentation, and the blurred boundaries of public and private spaces online. Teach how to manage visibility and protect personal data on social platforms.
- Target cyberbullying and risk behaviours head-on: include early prevention content on cyberbullying in all its forms (e.g., sextortion, impersonation, harassment). Promote empathy, responsible peer behaviour, and reporting mechanisms.
- Account for gender and vulnerability differences: tailor content to recognize how risks may differ based on gender, ability, and social context. Include relevant and sensitive strategies to help all children—especially those from vulnerable backgrounds—feel seen and supported.
- Build peer support and help-seeking behaviours: encourage a positive peer culture and empower children to help others online. Ensure children know where to seek help—at school, home, or through external channels.

Implications for the ASAP Educator Training Programme

- Focus on early detection and risk response: train educators to spot behavioural or emotional signs of digital distress—social withdrawal, changes in sleep or appetite, increased anxiety—and provide basic intervention skills or referral guidance.

- Support age-specific and developmental understanding: help educators understand the specific vulnerabilities of preadolescents, including impulsivity, identity formation, peer influence, and emotional intensity, and how these relate to online behaviour.
- Integrate mental health and digital skills: training should connect digital literacy with emotional and mental health. Provide educators with tools like check-ins, prompts, and case discussions to foster safer classroom conversations around digital life.
- Provide practical, flexible resources: offer ready-to-use materials, microlearning modules, and adaptable lesson plans that can fit into various teaching environments and curricula. This includes guidance for low-resource or decentralized contexts.
- Strengthen educators' empathy and communication capacity: training should improve teacher-student-parent communication, especially around sensitive topics like cyberbullying, social withdrawal, and screen overuse. Include scenario-based learning and collaboration with school counsellors.
- Build system-wide capacity: prepare school psychologists, counsellors, and teachers with specific roles/functions in the school such as "prevention methodologists" to lead interventions and embed consistent approaches across schools. Foster whole-school awareness and alignment.

The ASAP Key Recommendations for Stakeholders and Policymakers

- Begin formal digital citizenship education in primary education: national curricula should mandate early, inclusive, and age-appropriate digital education addressing literacy, safety, well-being, and responsible behaviour—particularly with the trend of early platform access.
- Ensure curriculum-policy alignment and resource availability: legislation must be matched with implementation support—schools need training, funding, and time to deliver digital education effectively. Bridge gaps between high-level policy and on-the-ground practice.
- Strengthen national coordination and monitoring: establish or enhance national agencies (e.g., eSafety Commissioner model) that provide up-to-date training, child-friendly resources, and secure reporting channels for children and families.
- Embed professional development in national education plans: require regular, mandatory teacher training in online safeguarding, digital literacy, and student well-being. Ensure this is a part of teachers' continuous professional development (CPD).
- Create cross-sector networks and partnerships: foster collaboration between schools, NGOs, social services, health sectors, and digital providers to support digital well-being holistically and sustainably. Leverage and scale good practices already in place.
- Include vulnerable and marginalized groups in strategy design: develop inclusive strategies and materials for children in care, those with disabilities, and those from low-income or marginalized communities. Ensure their access to safe and supportive digital learning environments.
- Promote safer design and regulation of platforms: recommend legislation to enforce safety-by-design principles, age verification, and content moderation tailored to underage users, including pressure on tech platforms to prioritize youth well-being.

DESK RESEARCH

This report is part of the Erasmus+ project ASAP – *A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education*.

It presents the transdisciplinary knowledge contributions prepared by project partners. In addition, the report summarises the key findings of partner countries desk research reports as well as the key findings of the other countries desk research report. In the end, the report provides implications for the ASAP project, based on the research findings.

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